

Master Thesis

Socio-economic comparison between second capitals *Saint Petersburg* and *Hamburg* focusing on productivity in 2016 – 2021

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Abstract

This thesis examines the impact of changes in the macroeconomic indicators Construction, Industrial Production, Services, Unemployment and Salary Levels on economic growth developments on city-level of the two twinning cities Hamburg and Saint Petersburg by means of multiple regression analysis under strong assumptions. It was possible to make almost all mentioned variables become significant predictors for economic growth in a trial-and-error approach, while optimizing for Root Square Mean Error. Results suggest complex interaction mechanisms between variables and ambiguous impact directions depending on the moment of observation. A plea for a more transparent and uniform tracking of macroeconomic fundamental variables on high frequency and regional level is made.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Especially in times of divergence between Russia and the West, harmonizing and synergetic research seems salutary. A new information barrier, like a reminder of the long forgotten cold war between both spheres, overtakes decades of coalescence. The focus of this thesis is to compare fundamental macro- and socioeconomic parameters and their impact on economic prosperity of the two twin-cities Saint-Petersburg and Hamburg in the years 2016 to 2021. In the ideal case, this will reveal similarities and divergences in underlying economic mechanisms. As the German economic apparatus is believed to be rather transparent, meritocratic and integer, it will serve as a benchmark for findings that we will find in the Russian economy.

The unique stance of the two “second-capitals / second-cities” of Germany and Russia, namely Hamburg and Saint Petersburg have exceptional bearings in both nations. They are both million-metropolises to intelligencia, wealth and culture. Like a funny coincidence, Russian president Wladimir Putin (who speaks fluent German) was born and grew up in Saint Petersburg, while former German chancellor Angela Merkel (who speaks fluent Russian) was born and grew up in Hamburg. Her successor, the current chancellor of Germany Olaf Scholz was for 7 years mayor of Hamburg, while his wife, the current first lady of Germany was also born in Hamburg. It is quite obvious that both cities have unique national positionings, big ports with a whole history of trade each. They are hubs for innovation and development, as well as for science in their corresponding regions.

Advantageously, the available recent data on Saint Petersburg captures the “natural state” of the Saint Petersburg economy before Corona, and the Corona transition phase of up to 2021. Thereafter, significant economic sanctions impacted the steady state development and most likely lead to a divergence from the previous path, interestingly for both Saint Petersburg and Hamburg.

1.2. Mutual Influence, International Relations and City Twinning

After World War 2, recovery in mutual relations between Russia and Germany were overdue. Under the most difficult political conditions, a twinning of the two cities Saint Petersburg and Hamburg was established in 1957, making it one of the oldest city relations between both nations. One of the main developmental drivers were Russian imperial unity in contrast to the trend of European decentralization. That said, a hanseatic cooperation dates back to the Middle Ages. German-Russian relations are complex, traumatic, but also illustrate longstanding cooperation on many levels rooted in conflict resolution, image building and mutual economic

interests. The first student exchange was organized in 1977 accompanying many institutions, which cooperate to this very day. Especially the Deutsch Russisches Forum e.V., the Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften, the School of Journalism, the Saint Petersburg State University and the University of Hamburg appear significant in that regard. The chamber of commerce in Hamburg organizes exchange programs for young Russian professionals with the support of the Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst. The Hamburg chamber of commerce has even a representative office in Saint Petersburg. Even in times of crisis, city cooperation's remain resilient due to umbrella corporations and frameworks provided by the respective city councils, but stand and fall with personal engagement of individuals. During the Corona Crisis that overshadowed the years 2020 to 2021, the city relations remained relatively stable and agile on city-levels. Most communication-channels were adapted to digital communication through modern technologies like Zoom, and Microsoft-Teams. ^{1 2}

Despite all this robustness, the present political crisis between Russia and Ukraine appears to have damaged the currently perceived relationship, when the actual Mayor of Hamburg, Dr. Peter Tschentscher, announced to abort the German-Russian week in a statement on 24th February 2022, the very same day of escalation. Thereafter a scheduled journey to Saint Petersburg was also cancelled with no further announcements yet (as of July 2022). ³

In General, Hamburg is richer (biannual budget of 14 bln. EUR, 25 000 EUR per capita according to Statista 2020). Hamburg is a leader in digital and medical technologies. The city budget of Saint Petersburg is comparable to EU-level with an amount of 7 bln. EUR (293 EUR per capita). This comparison does, however not take the diverging price-levels into account, which are strongly influenced by the varying financial exchange rate. Saint Petersburg is seen as a global transport and logistics hub, is enriched by large financial business and scientific centers, as well as a high level of innovation promotion. Furthermore, Saint Petersburg plays a key role in the industrial cluster of ship building, mechanical engineering, instrument making (production of machine tools), electrical engineering and products for the military-industrial complex. Moreover, the non-ferrous metallurgy, chemical- and light industries are being developed. Some important identifiable events include e.g., the Saint Petersburg Economic Forum and the Scarlet Sails Project. Both cities have immense sea-ports, which are very relevant for both history and local economies. ²

1.3. Relevance and Motivation

The motivation in choosing this specific research lies in several aspects. The first being that understanding the Saint Petersburg economy is especially interesting at this very moment, while half the democratic world tries to sanction the Russian economy. It seems appropriate to investigate beforehand in regards of the exact relevant aspects within the Saint Petersburg economy that truly matter. It is an open secret that Russian elites mostly only care about civil life in Moscow and in Saint Petersburg. Therefore, is important to look into the hard data.

A second aspect is that most literature that can be found in this context deals almost exclusively with the International Relations aspect between both cities with if at all only minor excurses into a superficial economic comparison. It is as if everyone is united in the belief that an extensive comparison between two cities of diverging societies is hardly comparable, like apples to pears. My opinion on this matter is that we do not do scientific discourse enough justice, if our modern strategic videogames point out a more complex understanding of economic mechanisms than our scientific discourse and literature. Certainly, there are barriers to overcome and strong assumptions necessary to conduct such a comparison. I am sure that I will be pretty outspoken with at least some of my approaches. ⁴

I do not wish to claim that the results of this thesis are accurate. Much more, I wish other researchers to be intrigued in doing a better job than me for other city-comparisons and thus give us maybe one day a world map, where we can investigate synergic relationships of the fundamental economic activities that govern all our lives. Throughout my academic studies I encountered many macroeconomic models about how the economy works. Almost none of them were reflecting reality, despite being theoretically sophisticated and complex. I want to stimulate an in-depth discourse on why an increase in a specific macroeconomic variable can have positive impact on the economy in one city, while having a negative impact on the growth of another. Then, it might be interesting to see if we can find similarities about city-economies that respond in similar ways to comparable economic shocks.

One apparent reason for the absence of mentioned research might be the cultural differences, data-limitations and lingual burdens. Although it is possible to translate most foreign texts and statistics with modern tools (like the AI-Translator DeepL), a manual verification is indispensable. This limits the circle of possible researchers to those that can examine literature and economic reports in both German and Russian languages. As a bilingual native for both German and Russian, who is accustomed to both cultural spheres, my value proposition is to accurately conduct a direct and fundamental socio-economic comparison to the best of my knowledge in the hope to find underlying similar or diverging economic mechanisms on the city-level.

Another key-feature of this research is that it is first of all on city-level. Most cross-country comparisons are conducted on the country-level, subconsciously assuming homogeneity within countries. This might be less fatal for smaller countries like Liechtenstein, but how much does the average Russian salary-rate really say about the salary in Moscow, or Irkutsk?

Moreover, most macro-economic research is year-based. Economists look at the past 50 years and make conclusions about whole decades, or even centuries. The modern economic environment is, however, fundamentally different from the economic environment before fast information transmission was possible. Hence, the assessment of decades will have only very little predictive power for the modern future. Recent, monthly-based research should grasp more of the actual processes dominating the ad-hoc economy.

1.4. Research Question

The essential idea of this thesis is to compare the fundamental socio- economic environments of Saint Petersburg and Hamburg. More accurately, the aim of this thesis is to compare the impact of fundamental economic city-level metrics, namely salary-levels, construction activities, industrial production and unemployment on the economic output of Saint Petersburg and Hamburg respectively. The goal is to create two comparable econometric models, which allow to benchmark the results against each other. A priori, it is assumed that the Hamburg reporting and economic mechanisms are already more transparent, meritocratic and integer in comparison to the Saint Petersburg economy, which is on the other hand arguably more of a blind spot from the view-point of Western society. Consequently, it seems appropriate to benchmark findings that emerge from examining the Saint Petersburg economy (in form of similarities, anomalies or differences) against the results originating from examination of the Hamburg city-level economy. In the best case, underlying mechanisms of the respective economies might be revealed, adding to our understanding of possible policy-action-sets and their predictive accuracy, as well as fuel further research on local economic characteristics. The world is eager to know why the Russian economy is unexpectedly robust.

2. Literature Review

In this section, we will discuss and reflect upon available research concerning economic comparisons between Hamburg and Saint Petersburg, as well as other relevant literature. I want to announce it from the beginning that there is little truly comparable literature on an economic comparison between Hamburg and Saint Petersburg. Usually, research falls into one of four far-reaching categories. The reason is that the research question has some very specific elements to it.

The first category of literature is concerned with specifically Hamburg and Saint Petersburg, but is usually written from the perspective of International Relations. As already referenced in the introductory chapter, Hamburg and Saint Petersburg are twinning cities. They have a whole history of cooperations and institutions that are managing the relationship. It is important to know and reference the background information to perceive the most complete picture. However, the economic focus in those papers (such as Vlaemnick 2021) is missing for the most part, only briefly mentioning very general income comparisons at best.^{1 2}

The second kind of literature focuses on country-level comparisons and involves both Russia and Germany as a whole. Such a general comparison is usually little telling, because the developmental stage of Saint Petersburg and Moscow are generally completely different from the rest of the country. Regarding Russia as a homogeneous economic hub and making comparisons about illusionary averages is hardly scientific. More scientific are definitely Reshetov et al. (2020), who research the mechanisms of the taxation system of Germany and Russia in a comparative analysis. Some even more interesting research is for example Tsedilin (2021), who is researching systematic differences in science funding between Russia and Germany coming to the conclusion that funding in Germany is rooted in the business sector and in Russia most scientific research is state-funded. Therefore, high-tech export-efficiency in Germany is 20-times higher, which suggests a fundamental reform in the Russian approach. Further Walter et al. (2012) compared tendencies of Entrepreneurship students in Russia and Germany in regards to their general tendencies and came to the conclusion that entrepreneurship in Russia is often rooted in economic necessity, while their German counterparts have more mental barriers to start with more complex and challenging business ideas.^{5 6 7}

In general, it is clear that there are immense amounts of general research, which includes both entities, Germany and Russia. However, most of it is usually specific and not really useful for an economic comparison between Hamburg and Saint Petersburg. Supposedly, researching on

country-level (usually disregarding local heterogeneities) is a more populist approach and reflects data-availability limitations on city-level.

The third type of publications deals with research that invents frameworks on how to compare two cities in a general context. An example might be Anthopoulos et al. (2015), who invented a framework consisting of six general dimensions, on which smart cities might be compared. A further example might be Jerabek et al. (2020), who came up with universal parameters, which might serve as KPI's. The aim was to make cities more comparable for politicians and thus enhance their decision-making effectiveness. Truth be told, finding indicators to compare cities is actually quite a dusty undertaking. Helland et al. (1998) already came up with performance indicators for a comparison among six Scandinavian cities in the past century. Additionally, Gonzáles and Carrillo (2012) invented even an algorithm, which conducts city-benchmarkings on an automated level by searching for commonly available data and evaluating it. ^{8 9 10 11}

Adapting such research to our case is once again sub-optimal, because we already found our own macroeconomic parameters of interest that concern us more than general dimensions, KPI's, parameters or algorithms.

The fourth and final general category of research is investigating general relationships between specific macroeconomic variables and growth. An example might be Tse and Ganesan (1997), who investigated the causal relationship between construction flows and GDP by method of the Granger causality. Back then, their finding suggested that GDP was contra-intuitively more volatile than construction in Hong Kong in the 1990s. Their chicken-egg solution was that GDP led the construction flows. Chowdhury et al. (2019) explored impacts of macroeconomic variables on GDP in Bangladesh during 1987 – 2015 and found that almost all their macroeconomic variables (such as inflation, household consumption expenditure growth and exchange rate) influenced GDP significantly positively. Only real interest rate remained insignificant. Although they use diverging macroeconomic variables, their preferred method of multiple regression analysis has certain similarities to the taken approach in this thesis. Another example of an investigation was conducted by Kibria et al. (2014), who explored the impact of interest rates, exchange rates, inflation and FDI on GDP growth of Pakistan. Their finding suggest that all variables have unidirectional causal effects on GDP growth. ^{12 13 14}

Overall, it becomes clear that research has been conducted either with similar entities, or with similar focus, or with similar approaches, but there is little to none research that shares focus with this thesis. The only exception being a paper by Gubina and Lebedev (2020), which compares the sea ports of Hamburg and Saint Petersburg in an economic comparison. Unfortunately, this very paper is not publicly available and even the Russian library, where the

title was listed could not provide me with the paper on query. It does exist and it is most likely relevant, but simply publicly unavailable. ¹⁵

One interesting fact regarding this topic might be that according to a harbor comparison conducted by Statista, which classified harbors around Europe according to freight volume in 2015, the Hamburg Port achieved a freight volume of 138 million tons, while the sea port of Saint Petersburg merely scratched a freight volume of 52 million tons within that year. Although the data describes only one specific year, this relative relation suggests that the Hamburg Port handles a workload of 2,65-times the size of its Russian equivalent. ¹⁶

3. Approach and Aim

The favored method of analysis is the econometric regression analysis. As the core idea is to regress economic output on different fundamental economic variables, the process starts with data-collection. First, we need to gather comparable time-series data for both regional economies, which is in detail described in Section 4.1. of this thesis. Initially, the plan was to compare the time-series in the years 2019 to 2021, so that we would have with 2019 a rather regular year (despite lagged effects of the Navalny Sanctions) and the corona years 2020 and 2021. However, after discussing this matter with Prof. Lucke (from the University of Hamburg), it became evident that we deal with rather unusual years and that seasonal effects would dominate the whole regression at such a low n , as $n=36$. Thereafter, the time-frame was extended to the maximum, of what the available data is limited to. This means 2015 – 2021 for Hamburg ($n=84$) and 2016 – 2021 for Saint Petersburg ($n=72$). Very initial regression results suggested already for Hamburg that $n=84$ leads to significantly different results than $n=72$. Consequently, it seemed necessary to restrict the core-Hamburg-analysis to $n=72$ as well for assurances of comparability. Months later, during the final stages of the thesis, this observation turned out to be groundless and a comparison with non-equal observation-counts appeared to be more efficient and precise.

Furthermore, initial results showed that (as in most time-series), both regressions are subject to strong positive serial correlation. Both models have similar Durbin-Watson scores of roughly 0,7. As a consequence the Prais-Winsten estimation plays a key role in the analysis to account for autocorrelation.

Finally, we will have a look at which fundamental variables predict economic output on city-level significantly, which ones do not, and try to come up with compelling interpretations that then

could become testable hypothesis in further research. We will examine possible outliers, homoscedasticity, heterogeneity and perform robustness checks.

Forecasting future developments appears to be in sight of fast current developments unfortunately a dead cause and will remain incomparable due to the paradigm-shift and change in steady-state-path of both economies since February 2022. In a nutshell, I have to admit that results might be rooted in economic co-integration, which breaks ever more apart.

4. Data

4.1. Data Sources

In the very first step, data selection had to be performed. With the support of doctorate Christina Maaß, we worked through an extensive list of possible explanatory variables which would have the potential to have explanatory power on the output of the Saint Petersburg economy. As an intuitive limitation, the official Saint Petersburg economic reports were seen. They are released on a monthly basis by the Economic Policy Committee and Strategic Planning of St. Petersburg and are the essential source for most economic data about Saint Petersburg. Usually, only the last 5 years are available and an excel support file is additionally released frequently, which does, however, not always match the published values. These reports were suggested to me by both Prof. Vladimir Sherov-Ignatev and Prof. Alexandra Koval, two of my former professors from the Department of World Economy at the Saint Petersburg State University. The yearly versions of the reports contain for the most part monthly values and are largely consistent. They are also the official versions of economic-data releases that are used by politicians and economists for policy inferences. Moreover, they are the only official reports that deal with overarching publicly available economic data.

The initial set of observed variables contained the following:

The ideal dependent variable for economic output of the Saint Petersburg economy would be the gross-regional product. Unfortunately, this metric is only published on a yearly basis. Thus, substitutional metrics had to be found. Two possible metrics, which were published in the reports were “Balanced Financial Results of Organizations” and “Turnover of Organizations”. In initial regressions, it became evident that turnover suits the purpose of this analysis superiorly and is representing the state of the economy better.

As a start, the explanatory variables “Average Nominal Salaries”, “Consumer Price Index”, “Unemployment Rate”, “Volume of Industrial Production” and “Volume of Construction” were

thought of as sophisticated predictors of an economic output on the city-level. Later on, when possible Omitted Variables were thought of and the construction of GDP was thought through, “Value of conducted Services” became a good extension to the list. Specific reports were also translated with the help of “DeepL”, a modern AI-based translator into English for accurate definition analysis and extensive understanding of the Russian, Cyrillic economic reports.

For the case of Hamburg, most data originated from the Statistical Office for Hamburg and Schleswig-Holstein (statistik-nord.de). Similar data, but also similar problems were encountered in the twin-process. The statistical office offers an intuitive GUI user interface with an excel-export function. This made the data collection process easier in comparison to reading through individual monthly reports and writing them over manually by hand, as was the case for most Russian data. Unfortunately, the economic output in form of monthly GRP values is also unavailable for Hamburg. GRP values are released bi-annually and even the authors of the Hamburg economic reports could not provide me with any additional frequency of data. The best alternative that I was able to locate turned out to be the HASPAX index. The HASPAX index is a financial index, which tracks the performance of listed companies in the Hamburg metropolitan region. Although the index has its limitations and is certainly not a perfect representation of the Hamburg economy, it turned out to be quite sophisticated in the conducted regression analyses. My values for the HASPAX index were skimmed from the n-tv.de stock exchange archive for the reason of good data availability and an absence of reasons to assume incorrect values. Furthermore, I ran into several problems with frequencies for the Hamburg data, because e.g., salary-levels are released on a quarterly basis. The taken solution took the form of cubic interpolation to increase the value-frequencies to monthly. Although it might decrease accuracy, we will see later when examining the data that the Hamburg economy is rather slow-moving and that even in Corona-years the economy is rather robust. The same statement would not be true for the Saint Petersburg economy, because the Saint Petersburg data is way rougher and responds with all kind of rough spikes to economic shocks. A similar problem for Saint Petersburg would not be that easily solvable by interpolation. For the Hamburg economy on the other hand, such an approach seems appropriate. Later on, when adding services to the regression analysis as a further explanatory variable, it turned out that the Hamburg statistical office is not really dealing with information on the service sector (especially not in monthly frequency). The chosen bypass was to take the values of the index of the “climate of the service industry”, which is published by the Hamburg chamber of commerce (ihk.de).

While it is arguable that both data-sets for the two economies have their nuances and small differences, they are for the most part very similar and the best, which public data availability

seems to offer at this time. Certainly, with better data and data accuracy, a better analysis and results could be expected. There are unfortunately limitations to data availability, frequency, and practical measuring.

4.2. Data Description

In this section, we will look through time-series of all relevant variables for both cities. As inflation is known to inflate all monetary values, adjusting all values to a single time-data-point should in theory make the values more comparable across different years. Although it is clear that inflation is heterogenous across industries and that no generally applicable inflation can be found, the consumer price index (CPI) is a metrics, which is available in the data-set for both cities. Moreover, in Saint-Petersburg the Industrial Price Index is also available (and indeed very similar to the CPI values), but for the sake of simplicity and limitations faced in the Hamburg data, all monetary values will be in an initial step deflated by the CPI. The point in time, which will be regarded as base is going to be arbitrarily January 2018.¹⁷

A further inevitable problem is that we deal with different currencies. Euro in Hamburg, and Ruble in Russia. This makes interpretation of results and comparison harder due to the fact that exchange rates are floating. The taken solution to this was to take the average exchange rate of again January 2018 (1 EUR = 69,91 RUB). Hence, we perceive everything from the frozen perspective of January 2018.

All concrete definitions of the explored variables can be examined in the appendix, or the enclosed excel file, which additionally deals with all the numeric values for all variables.

4.2.1. Consumer Price Index in Hamburg

Figure 1: CPI Hamburg 2015 – 2021.

Figure 1 originates from the published values for CPI by the “Statistisches Amt für Hamburg und Schleswig-Holstein” in monthly frequency. In general, we see an up-wards trend, which was visibly fueled by the Corona-crisis. The basis for the CPI is a statistical basket of goods containing approx. 700 goods and the basket is updated on an ongoing basis. For Figure 1 it means that the basket was in December 2021 10,6% more expensive compared to March 2016. In the time-frame of 7 years, the dotted trendline increased by around 10%. Thus, we could hypothetically talk about a CPI-based inflation of roughly 1,4% per year, which is close to the long aimed for 2 percent of the ECB. ¹⁸

In the next step, we transform Figure 1 and make the value of Jan 2018 equal to 100%. This results in Figure 2. The values shown in Figure 2 become our inflation adjustment distribution key, which we will apply to all monetary values for Hamburg.

Figure 2: Inflation Index as of January 2018.

4.2.2. Consumer Price Index in Saint Petersburg

Before taking a closer look at the Consumer Price Index for Saint Petersburg, we have to emphasize that regarding the consumer price index as a proxy for general inflation is a limitation. The official Saint Peterburg Socio Economic Development Reports (yearly published with monthly frequencies) deal also with for example with the Producer Price Index and an Index of tariffs for freight transportation. Although all those indices are very close to each other, they still differ. Inflation is very heterogeneous and differs across industries, sectors, and product-types. Assuming that this one value of Consumer Price Index is a perfect representation of overall (or maybe average) inflation within the economy is a very strong and limiting assumption. Nonetheless, it is probably the best available metrics and does represent overall

inflation to a certain degree. Furthermore, such an assumption allows for simplicity and is available in very comparable forms for both observed cities.

Figure 3: Official Inflation in Saint Petersburg 2019 – 2021.

Figure 3 illustrates the inflation in Saint Petersburg in the years 2019 – 2021. It is rooted in the official economic reports and differs in the way it is presented. The CPI in Hamburg was illustrated as a ratio in a specific month compared to some specific base-month. In Figure 3 in contrast, we see a monthly inflation rate. For example, the CPI value in January 2017 amounts to 1,3%. This means that in January prices grew by 1,3 percent. The graph looks quite volatile and random, but also seems to be stable.

Another point with the inflation in Russia, which is worth being aware of is that the official inflation might not be the real occurring inflation in the country, or in this case the city of Saint Petersburg. There is no evidence that the official inflation rate is completely made up, but inconsistencies might exist in the way it is calculated.¹⁹

Transforming the Saint Petersburg CPI similarly, as we did for Hamburg, we end up with Figure 4.

Figure 4: Inflation as ratio to January 2018.

In Figure 4, we see the transformed inflation rate for Saint Petersburg, if once again January 2018 is taken as base. Figure 4 also shows the same transformed CPI-Inflation for Hamburg to have a graphical comparison. It is obvious that the inflation in Saint Petersburg is

stronger in comparison to stable Hamburg. Nonetheless, I personally would have expected an even bigger difference after living in Saint Petersburg for almost a year. I personally do believe that inflation within the regarded frame in Saint Petersburg was higher than we see in Figure 4. Nevertheless, we will work with the official numbers in this research, because they are simply the best that we have available. Data-availability is one of the limiting factors in this research.

Summarized, we will divide all monetary values for both cities by the values shown in Figure 4 to adjust for inflation. Inflation is believed to make all the monetary units blurry, because we cannot tell if a certain increase was due to inflation or some real economic spike. It seems thus justified to adjust everything for inflation and look at all monetary numbers through the lens of January 2018. January 2018 was chosen randomly as the base anchor.

Moreover, it would be more comprehensible to compare both results in the same monetary unit. Hence, all the Russian Ruble monetary units will be converted into Euro equivalents. The chosen conversion rate of 69,9062 Rubles per 1 Euro was the average conversion rate in January 2018. This conversion will allow us to compare apples with apples, although we face some limitations to this analogy as well due to different price levels. We will have to take this face into consideration when interpreting the results.

4.2.3. Economic Output as Dependent Variable

In the very best scenario, we would have monthly GDP data for both cities and then regress the city GDP on all the variables that we think are impactful (and available). Unfortunately, GDP, or better said Gross Regional Product in our case is only available with a strong delay and also in bi-annual frequency at best. Contacting the Statistische Bundesamt and its Russian equivalent, as well as talking with several professors about this merely confirmed the suspicion that monthly data is simply not available. The taken solution was to work with the HASPAX index for Hamburg and with the “Turnover of Organizations” for Saint Petersburg.

4.2.3.1. The HASPAX Index - Hamburg

The HASPAX Index, which is a financial index and measured in performance points is the closest reflection of the monthly Hamburg economy on monthly basis available to the public. The Index tracks the performance of listed companies in the Hamburg metropolitan region and has also a few safety measures to prevent very big companies to dominate the whole index. The maximum weighting per share is limited to 15 percent. The used values of the HASPAX index were written off by hand from the n-tv stock price archive. ²⁰

Figure 5 shows the HASPAX Index on monthly frequency. After adjusting for inflation and expressing it in January 2018 prices, the index seems to not change visually in a fundamental way. We see that the index grew within the 7 years of observation from 3000 to 6000 performance points. This increase seems a little suspicious because the Gross Regional Product of Hamburg according to Eurostat was 108 bln. EUR in 2015 and became 119 bln. EUR in 2020. This is merely an increase by 10 percent and does not adjust for inflation. Reasons might be that the inflation for financial products is completely different from the CPI-based inflation. Another reason might be the frugality of the local Hamburg population and their continued search for financial investments. Moreover, it is also possible that listed companies simply perform better than the average market (economics of scale). In the end, the HASPAX index is nonetheless the best representation of the local economy available and will serve as a representation of the economic output of Hamburg in the analysis.

4.2.3.2. Turnover of Organizations – Saint Petersburg

Just as for Hamburg, GRP data for Saint Petersburg is not available in the right frequency. There were two competing variables that were tested. The first was the “Balanced Financial Results” of all companies in Saint Petersburg. The alternative was the Turnover of Organizations in Saint Petersburg. In early analysis it became evident that Financial Results is a suboptimal dependent variable and representor for the Saint Petersburg Economy. The Turnover of Organizations on the other hand became the chosen Y-variable for the Saint Petersburg regression.

Figure 5: Development of the HASPAX Index 2015 – 2021.

Nonetheless, let’s have a quick look at Figure 6, which shows the Balanced Financial Results in Russian Ruble in the years 2016 to 2021. Especially evident are the unusual spikes in late 2020 and second half of 2021. It is possible that they are rooted in the impact of the Corona pandemic, which was first noticed in late 2020. Furthermore, there are several months with negative financial results (such as February 2018). Especially towards the end of the observation period, the shown spikes seem suspicious of either ever more frequent outliers, or some inflationary

trend. Adjusting for the official inflation has very little visual effect as can be seen when comparing the yellow and the blue graph. All values can be viewed in the Excel Master-Sheet, which compliments this thesis.

Figure 6: *Balanced Financial Result of companies registered in Saint Petersburg, Russia.*

Figure 7 on the other hand deals with information on the turnover of companies in Saint Petersburg in the years 2016 to 2021. Once again, we see that something happened in late 2020. In the final quantile the values seem unusually inflationary, which seems to indicate a change in trend. Expressing the turnover in January 2018 prices leads to the blue graph. It constitutes our basis for the representation of the Saint Petersburg economy and hence is our dependent variable.

Figure 7: *Turnover of Organizations registered in Saint Petersburg in the years 2016 - 2021.*

Figure 8 is an equivalent to Figure 7 and has all values divided by the average RUB to EUR conversion-rate of January 2018. This rate is 69,9062 Rubel per Euro. From this graph we see that usually the companies in Saint Petersburg were having a monthly turnover of somewhere between 10 billion and 20 billion Euros. This trend breaks towards the end of the observation period and ends at a staggering value of almost 35 billion Euros in December 2021. Also, it is visibly recognizable that there is some form of seasonality. The values increase usually towards the fourth quarter of every year and drop towards the first quarter.

Figure 8: Turnover of Organizations in Saint Petersburg in the years 2016 to 2021. Converted to January 2018 Euros.

4.2.4. Variable: Unemployment

In the next sections I would like to discuss further variables that will be part of the analysis. Let us begin with a visual overview of the unemployment development in both cities. Unemployment level is a critical indicator of the overall well-being of any economy. A high rate might indicate sectoral frictions or inefficiencies. Besides the pure metric interpretation, there are also safety concerns that go hand-in-hand with a high unemployment rate.

4.2.4.1. Unemployment in Hamburg

Figure 9: Unemployment in Hamburg 2015 - 2021.

Figure 9 shows the unemployment in Hamburg. Germany has a very unique, world famous social security system, which allows all inhabitants to live a life in dignity. As the two graphs in Figure 9 show, there is a gap between unemployed people and people, who receive funding from the state. In this context it is important to mention that citizens (including tolerated persons) that earn less than the social security are stocked up to this minimal level. Thus, it is possible for a person to have a job and still receive ALG2 (for example by working in a 450 EUR so called “mini-job”). The blue graph on the other hand shows the registered people that are literally not working, but able and hopefully willing to work. The blue graph is the variable that will be taken into further analysis. Moreover, worth-mentioning is the incentive in Germany to really register as unemployed due to state-funding.

Looking at the blue graph it seems that the amount of unemployed people is stagnating and even slightly decreasing through most of the observation period. Again, in mid-2020, we see a change in the trend and a lasting note-worthy increase in unemployment numbers. In December 2021, we can talk again about a normal month with approx. 70 000 unemployed persons.

Figure 10: Social Security Contributors in Hamburg 2015 – 2021 in quarterly frequency.

Another interesting metrics is surely the amount of people funding this whole system, as graphed in Figure 10. In Hamburg, a lot of the state-funding is rooted in the social security contribution of the working population. Interestingly, we see a slight positive trend during the observation period. This is definitively a good development. However, it becomes obvious that with an approx. population of 1,8 million and a working population of 974 000 (average value within observation period), only every second person is engaged in an employment that results in social security contributions. In reverse this means that almost 53% of the population do not directly contribute by means of social security contributions. This obviously also includes children, elderly and similar groups. Nonetheless, the positive trend seems very healthy for the economy.

4.2.4.2. Unemployment in Saint Petersburg

In contrast to Germany, there is little incentive for registering as unemployed in the true case of unemployment. It seems thus driven by absence of incentives that a lot of the non-employed population never registers as unemployed with the state and thus does not appear within the official statistics. Nonetheless, changes in the available unemployment rate might provide interesting information.

Figure 11 shows the official unemployment statistics in the city of Saint Petersburg, Russia. The data is divided into the number of non-occupied people (blue graph) and our chosen variable for unemployment in Saint Petersburg (yellow graph). The yellow graph shows the number of people that are registered by the state as unemployed by the end of a month.

The very first striking observation is the spike in unemployment rate in 2020, most likely due to lockdowns and pandemic. Personal acquaintances of mine describe that many people worked in the shadow economy during the initial strict lockdowns due to a lack of social welfare by the state. Many people worked from home in the non-controlled shadow economy.

Figure 11: Unemployment in Saint Petersburg 2015 – 2021.

In Hamburg we had an average of 72 000 people at a population of 1,8 million that were registered as unemployed (=4% of the total population). In Saint Petersburg it is an average of 25 000 non-employed people at a population of approx. 5 million (=0,5%). This means that in Hamburg are 8x as many people registering as unemployed in relative terms. Reasons for this might be the different incentives. Good social benefits in Germany, and almost none in Russia. Furthermore, a person can have a sufficient living without working in Germany. The same is not true in Russia and thus most of the people really work, or find practical means to survive. This is certainly reflected in the substantially bigger shadow economy in Russia, where a very big part of the population does not believe in taxes and never paid them (or at least attempts to avoid taxation). The persecution of tax-avoidance in Russia is absolutely ineffective and there is probably little incentive (even by politicians) to make it an effective process.²¹

In conclusion we can say that probably more people register in Hamburg when unemployed compared to Saint Petersburg. However, we can see clear and to some extent similar spikes in both rates.

4.2.5. Variable: Salary Level

Another trackable explanatory variable to reflect the well-being of an economy might be the development of salaries. Salary-level might in some instances be connected to the inflation rate, but also provide valuable insights into economic mechanisms when perceived as an indicator and once again adjusted for theoretical inflation.

4.2.5.1. Salary Developments in Hamburg

The very first issue when dealing with salary developments in Hamburg on monthly frequency is that the data is released quarterly only. Figure 12 below shows the development from 2015 to 2021. The first visible trend is that it is increasing and that it has a slight set-back around March 2020 (probably due to the corona pandemic). In general, the salary level grew from around 4 000 EUR to approx. 4 700 EUR within 7 years, which is an increase by 17,5%.

Figure 12: Gross Monthly Earnings of full-time employees in manufacturing and services 2015 – 2021.

One viable approach to transform quarterly data into monthly is by means of interpolation. More particular cubic spline interpolation provides us with approximate interim values. Xiong (2021) already discussed that cubic spline interpolation interims produce only neglectable errors and has little impact on statistical inference. Figure 13 represents the salary-development in Hamburg in monthly frequency. The blue graph is taking CPI-inflation into account and corrects for it. A slight positive trend, as indicated by the blue dotted trend-line persists. Nonetheless, the real increase in wages after correcting for inflation is significantly smaller. Wages start at about 4 100 EUR and end up at approx. 4 350 EUR, which is merely an increase of 5,9 percent (a little over a third of the perceived increase from Figure 12.).²²

Figure 13: Salary Development in Hamburg 2015 – 2021.

Further information we obtain by looking into the month-over-month changes in the developments (basically the first-difference), as illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Hamburg Salary Development month-over-month 2015 – 2021.

In later analysis it became obvious that the trend shown in Figure 13 can be seen as stationary, because both stationarity tests (Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test for Unit Root and Phillips-Perron Unit Root Test) show with $p=0,01$ and $p=0,02$ accordingly that the salary development is in fact stationary. Nonetheless, looking at Figure 14, we can see that changes within a specific month can vary somewhere between 1,3 and -1,6 percent. The extreme visible drop happened as mentioned already around March 2020 during the first lockdown in Germany that was offset by a correction in following periods.

4.2.5.2. Salary Developments in Saint-Petersburg

Figure 15: Salary Developments in Russian Rubles in Saint Petersburg 2016 - 2021.

Salary developments in Saint-Petersburg in the years 2016 to 2021 differ slightly visually from the German counter-part. Figure 15 shows a slight positive trend with very periodic spikes each year around Christmas. Most likely, this accounts for possible bonus payments to employees for New Year, which appears to be even of more significance in the Russian culture than in the

German. We also observe that correcting for CPI-inflation seems especially important in the last two observed years, as indicated by the increasing gap between yellow and blue graph. Converting the monetary unit from Rubles into Euros gives us Euro-heavy interpreters a better comparison to the Hamburg equivalent.

Figure 16 shows us the development in Euros increasing from around 700 EUR to almost 1 000 EUR as indicated by the dotted trend-line. This is an increase of almost 43 percent and already adjusted for inflation.

Figure 16: Saint Petersburg Salary Developments in EUR; adjusted for CPI-inflation.

A possible interpretation might be that Russia is catching up. The spikes can be seen as periodic outliers, as the Christmas-salary is not a valid representation of average salary, but is nevertheless a part of it.

Figure 17: Month-over-month salary development in Saint Petersburg 2019 – 2021.

Once again looking at the month-over-month change in Figure 17, we can see that salary in December is usually a third higher compared to all other months. One reason might be the pressure to finish a year well in December, followed by a holiday-intense January. Furthermore, normal fluctuations range from -8 to 10 percent in non-December months. This suggests that the fluctuations are higher and thus salary-stability of an employee in Russia is significantly lower

compared to the ± 1 percent fluctuations in Hamburg. We also know that Russia still has many rich people, but not due to employment. Being employed in Russia and being part of the official statistics will most likely not provide an individual with a decent living-standard. This might provide room for a giant out-of-statistics shadow economy with very wealthy people paying no taxes. Truth be told, the salary developments do not look like they are random of nature, but show rather very seasonal, maybe even fate-full developments. Especially compared to the random-walk like-appearing month-over-month changes for the Hamburg time-series. ²³

4.2.6. Variable: Industrial Production

One of the presumably very important indicators for the well-being of an economy is certainly industrial output. When calculating the GDP of a country (which is still seen as the status-quo representer of the economic level), then some macroeconomic core components are consumption, investment and exports. All three are heavily influenced by the industrial production output, which determines to a part the quantity of exports, requires investment and allows for consumption. Gokmenoglu et al. (2015) already explored that GDP and industrial production are integrated to the order of 1, $I(1)$ according to the Phillips-Perron test. Zinchenko et al. (2017) even name overcoming technological inefficiencies in industrial production as a key goal for economic development. Thus, it is clear that at least in theory, analyzing the economy has to involve a cross-section to industrial production. ^{24 25}

4.2.6.1. Industrial Production in Hamburg

In Hamburg, industrial production is essentially the combination of the output of the manufacturing industry (Figure 18) together with the energy and water production (Figure 19), which has, however, only very little relative impact. For sake of completion and because the industrial production in Saint Petersburg includes also both composites, it should be composed as shown in Figure 20.

Figure 18: Hamburg Manufacturing Industry 2015 - 2021.

Figure 19: Hamburg energy and water supply 2015 - 2021.

Figure 20 composites the chosen Industrial Production variable for Hamburg. As indicated by the dotted trend-line there is even after adjustment for inflation a slight positive trend indicating that the economy is indeed experiencing a positive development. Surprisingly we see a strong positive correction after the corona drop surpassing even previous highs, which indicates that the pressures of home-office and lockdowns might even have led to technological productivity shocks. On average, the industrial production in Hamburg valued to 6,2 billion Euros per month.

Figure 20: Hamburg Manufacturing Industry 2015 - 2021.

Figure 21 illustrates the monthly changes in percent. We can clearly see that industrial production dropped once in Q1 2020 by approximately 25 percent. This was, however, followed by several extraordinary months as illustrated by the five positive spikes, each at least accounting for a 10 percent increase.

Figure 21: Industrial Variance in Hamburg 2015 - 2021.

4.2.6.2. Industrial Production in Saint Petersburg

Industrial development in Saint Petersburg was unfortunately not as fruitful. Figure 22 shows a clear decline of industrial production, which is even more evident when adjusting for inflation.

Figure 22: Industrial Production in Saint Petersburg 2016 - 2021. In Russian Rubles.

Converting Figure 22 into our currency of choice leads us to Figure 23. Evidently, conversion by scaling does not relieve us of the ever evident downwards fall of industrial production in Saint Petersburg. It appears that when globalization was still an ideal to strive for back in 2021, the industry of Saint Petersburg was not really capable of competing on world markets.

Figure 23: Industrial Production in Saint Petersburg 2016 – 2021 in Euros.

Industrial production dropped from highs of over 15 billion Euros to around mere 3,8 billion Euros. At this stroke of fate, the corona pandemic appears even invisible in regards to the yearly, predictable drops to each 1st of January. Nonetheless, the average of around 6 billion Euros makes the industry very comparable to Hamburg's average of 6,2 billion. Just as all previous Russian indicators, this one seems also very seasonal and of high variance. At this point it is worth mentioning that the absolute numbers of industrial production were never published in absolute values. Only the monthly developments in percent can be found in official reports. This might actually be a form of concealment. It was, nevertheless, not too complicated to compile the values based on their monthly changes and the fact that the aggregated industrial turnover in 2019 amounted to 3 835 billion Ruble, as was published in the official yearly report for 2019.

There is also a possibility that my calculations are wrong, or that the reports are not truly reflecting reality, because such an important metrics as industrial production might provide space for exploitation by competing world powers. It would on first sight, however, appear sub-optimal to simply blur out the extent of downturn instead of selling it as upturn.

Figure 24: Month-over-month development of Industrial Production in Saint Petersburg (2016 - 2021).

Figure 24, which illustrates the month-over-month changes (first difference) only confirms what was already observed in Figure 23. In January we have always suspicious adjustments of up to 45%, as happened in January 2018. Strong seasonal effects seem to exist.

4.2.7. Variable: Construction

The next economic variable that will be examined is “construction”. Strong construction-levels might indicate a local growth, attraction of citizens and companies to modern environments and the creation of usable infrastructure, which should theoretically benefit the economy in both, short- and long-term. Modernizing and repairing existing infrastructure are conservational measures.

4.2.7.1. Construction in Hamburg

Figure 25: Construction-Volume in Hamburg 2015 - 2021.

Figure 25 is a general representation of construction-activities in Hamburg between 2015 and 2021. We see a slight positive trend during most of the observation period. Especially the boom towards November 2021 indicates augmented investments. Construction seems to be a very

seasonal and cyclic activity, which experiences regular drops in January of each year. On average, 150 million Euros are spent on construction activities. This is merely 2% of the average industrial production (6,2 billion Euros). Thus, construction is contrary to popular belief not a fundamental driver of economic output, but solely an indicator with probably long-lasting accumulative indirect effects.

Figure 26: First Difference of Construction in Hamburg 2015 - 2021.

A brief look at Figure 26 shows that the growth-rate in the variable “construction” experiences very cyclic patterns, maybe even reminding of a human heart-beat.

Overall construction looks almost boring during most of the observation period. In winter, it is cold and construction decreases. In lockdowns, there are less opportunity costs to closing down facilities and infrastructure for modernization. Hence, the Corona lockdown seems to have led to a positive boost to construction in Hamburg.

4.2.7.2. Construction in Saint Petersburg

Figure 27: Construction in Saint Petersburg.

Figure 27 illustrates construction in Saint Petersburg during 2016 to 2021. The first observation might be that inflation (the way it is measured in this thesis) has no significant adjustment effect on construction. Furthermore, we see a giant spike in December 2016 that makes all other fluctuations appear diminutive. Such adjustments for December 2016 can also be observed in

many other Russian cities according to the Excel file. A comment concerning December 2016 for all cities says “Data adjusted based on revised reports submitted by respondents.”. This suggests inconsistencies in reporting. Moreover, the graph is in Russian Rubles and thus we need to forego through some modifications before attempting to interpret it.

Figure 28: Construction in Saint Petersburg in EUR throughout the years 2016 to 2021.

Figure 28 shows the same graph as Figure 27, but in January 2018 Euros. Now we see that construction amounts to an average of 592 million Euros per month. December 2016 amounts to 3,9 billion Euros and is 6,6-times the average. We can categorize this month as exceptional and exclude it from our observation as a clear outlier. The average construction value is with 592 million per month approx. 9,7 percent of the average industrial output that has an average of 6,09 billion Euros. Therefore, construction seems to have a stronger impact on the economy compared to Hamburg, where the ratio is only around 2 percent.

Figure 29: SPB Construction in Euros excluding December 2016 as outlier.

Figure 29 shows us a very different picture compared to the previous graphs 27 and 28. By excluding the outlier (Dec2016), we get a far more telling picture. We see strong seasonal movements with decreases in January and reliefs during spring. Over the whole period, the trend is mostly stagnating. There is a miniscule decrease throughout the period as indicated by the trend-line, but we can rather talk about a very stable stagnation. Furthermore, we do not see a boom during 2021 that might have been triggered by a lockdown. Having some background-

knowledge about both cities, I claim it true that maintenance of for example entrance halls in Russia is in general not seen as part of the owned property, but rather common space that is rooted in a free-rider problem. Most entry-halls look runic and the state does not appear to have the necessary resources to modernize the thousands of architecturally demining palaces and old buildings. New constructions are mostly of practical and efficient nature.

Figure 30: Construction in Saint Petersburg first difference (2016 - 2021).

For the sake of completion, we are also taking a quick look at the changes in Figure 30, which are little telling, except for having a rather strong volatility and being subject to seasonal effects.

4.2.8. Variable: Services

Our last and final variable of attention is “services”. It was an additional variable that was included in later stages of the analysis when searching for omitted variables and asking the question what BIP might further include. Obviously, services are the other half of output besides industrial production and should be attended to in the analysis. Unfortunately, especially in Hamburg, the measurement of services seems to have some secretive component.

4.2.8.1. Services in Hamburg

There are two problems with the service sector in Hamburg. The first one is that there is simply a lack in transparency. The very best representation of the service sector in Hamburg is the “Climate in the service industry”. It is an indicator, which is “derived from the assessment of the current situation and future development”. Speaking plainly, it is not absolutely clear, whether the index, which is ranging between 1 and 200 has only a quantitative foundation, or also a qualitative. It might have similar issues as the HASPAX index, which was the first substitute taken into account. It is published by the Hamburg Chamber of Commerce (Handelskammer Hamburg) and is thus the most trusted source available.

The second problem is that the index is published with a quarterly frequency and hence interpolation is necessary to transform the data into the right frequency. Consequently, the data diverges probably even further from some theoretical “real value”. Figure 31 is the

representation of the service sector in Hamburg. The yellow graph in Figure 31 is simply connecting the values with a straight line, while the blue line is the cubic interpolation.

Figure 31: Representation of the service sector in Hamburg 2015 - 2021.

There are 3 observations that I would like to make about this graph. The first is that it seems to be subject to a slight decline as indicated by the linear trendline. In general, it is believed that the service sector in Germany becomes ever more important due to a loss in industrial competitive edge against e.g., China and a strong focus on the service sector from thereon.²⁶

The second and third observation are pendants to each other, namely the index-spike in Q1 2017 and the Corona-drop in Q1 2020. At this point I have to add that I fully trust the drop in Q1 2020, because it was caused by the very obvious and impacting forced lockdowns of the German economy during the beginning of the pandemic. The Q1 2017 spike on the other hand looks suspicious to me, because a pendant to the Q1 2020 drop in form of a spike would have not gone unnoticed. There simply was no event that might have a similar positive magnitude as the complete shutdown of the economy. Therefore, I am inclined to believe that it is a qualitative result rooted in optimism and not market measurement of the service sector. Nonetheless, these data-values are the best available. Even in the 2020s transparency of local German economies on city-level seem to be an issue. We might be in dire need of the German “Wirtschaftsweisen” or Economic Sages to tell expert stories on the state of the economy, in cases where we cannot scientifically track and analyze the data. I do believe at this point that there should be a lot done to increase transparency of the economy in Germany, although Hamburg is probably already one of the most transparent cities within the German economy.

4.2.8.2. Services in Saint Petersburg

In Saint Petersburg, there is a monthly metrics published dealing with the volume of consumptions of services by the population. It is not absolutely clear, how this metrics is tracked, but it exists alongside all the other published metrics. One thought to keep in mind is that there is a big shadow-economy, especially in the hard-to-track service sector. Many service-providers

do not pay any taxes, do not print receipts and are thus certainly not within the tracked numbers. After living for a year in Saint Petersburg, I know this to be true and at very large scale. Podshivalova (2021) explains that tax avoidance in Russia is rooted in historical and cultural developments involving the suspension of anti-tax-avoidance techniques by the ministries in the soviet government aera. In the 1990s, it is estimated that 30% of the taxes were never collected. I personally believe this number to have been even larger. Especially in the criminal 1990s “thieves-in-law” aera.²¹

Figure 32: Service Sector in Saint Petersburg 2016 - 2021 in Russian Rubles.

Figure 32 shows us the volume of the service sector in Saint Petersburg during the observation period. It deals with the so far biggest visual divergence before and after adjusting for inflation, as indicated by the growing gap between the yellow and blue graph.

Figure 33: Service sector in Saint Petersburg in Euros.

Figure 33 is a conversion of the blue graph of Figure 32 into January 2018 Euros. We see that the volume of services provided ranges from almost 400 million Euros during the Corona Lockdown to an often-scratched maximum of almost 670 million Euros. The average of 585 million Euros is indicating that the upper values seem more robust than the lower values. Furthermore, we see a slight positive development of the Service Sector overall. It is not easy to see, but the decline during lockdown seems in fact smaller than in Hamburg, which is a weird finding to say the least in view of the robust German social state. The average in the German index was 120 and the lowest value 45. This results in a drop of 62,5 percent. The Saint Petersburg obviously more

volatile service sector fell only by approximately 32 percent. This would indicate that the Saint Petersburg service sector (if believing the numbers) would be twice as robust as the Hamburg service sector. The fact that we have an index (with probably qualitative elements) on one hand and a measured metrics on the other hand prevents us from proofing this observation. It remains an unexpected finding nonetheless. Moreover, there was an adjustment for inflation in the numeric values, but most likely no adjustment for inflation in the index-based-counterpart.

4.3. Demographic comparison

In this final part of Section 4, I want to compare the demographic characteristics of both cities and their implications for the respective economies.^{27 28}

Figure 34 and 35 show the respective population age distribution in thousands. The very first obviousness is that people in Hamburg reach a higher age and due to the German social contract require more funding from the working population. It is a widely known problem that is politically often used to justify migration. In 2020, Hamburg had a total population of 1,85 million people. The average dying age of males is 78,7 years and of females 83,5 years as of 2019.²⁹

Figure 34: Demographics Hamburg in 2020.

Figure 35: Demography in Saint Petersburg on 01.01.2021

In Saint Petersburg, the total population amounts to 5,5 million people (3-times as many citizens as in Hamburg). Male life-expectancy at birth is 72 years and 80 years for females, which is slightly less than in Hamburg, as of 2019. Moreover, the gap in life-expectancy between both genders is larger.³⁰

Both cities face the dangerous trend of an ever-older growing population, as can be seen on the typical bellies on the age-distribution figures, a low fertility rate and underrepresented youth. While the average age in Saint Petersburg is approximately 41,6 years, the average age in Hamburg is already 42,2 years. A very minor difference. ³¹

Overall, we can say that both cities face very similar challenges on the future labor markets, when the boomer generations become pensioners. It is also clear that the pensioners will harvest more on the economy in the social state Hamburg, because the average pension in Saint Petersburg amounts to merely 18 415,5 ruble, which is about 265 Euros per month without any further social safety nets like housing subsidies. ³²

According to Statistikamt Nord, the average rent in Hamburg amounts to 1 275 Euros per month in 2020 and is hence larger by a factor of almost 5-times. Such a big gap makes the Russian pension system appear more sustainable.

5. Analysis

Section 5 is the investigative component of this thesis, which will focus on scientific exploration of the presented data. The key task will be to investigate, whether the proposed regression models fulfil necessary requirements for validity.

5.1. Econometric Modelling

When trying to model the available data, I would like to start with the most intuitive Regression in alignment with the idea of Ockham's Razor. All Regressions were executed with SPSS 28. Most conscious ideas on econometric modelling are taken from the Wooldridge Introductory Econometrics Sixth Edition book. ³³

A very intuitive model might look like this: $Y = X_1 + X_2 \dots + X_n + u$

This would mean for Saint Petersburg:

$$SPB_TurnoverOrg_{J18E} = IndustProd_{J18E} + Salaries_{J18E} + Constr_{J18E} + Services_{J18E} + Unempl + u$$

Note: Subscript J18E means deflated to January 2018 and converted into Euros.

For Hamburg, the equation might look like:

$$HH_Haspax_{J18} = IndustProd_{J18} + Salaries_{J18} + Constr_{J18} + ServiceIndex + Unempl + u$$

However, when regressing both equations, it became obvious that as usually in time-series the regression is subject to positive serial correlation. Both regressions showed a Durbin-Watson value between 0,6 (SPB) and 0,8 (HH). This meant that a significant positive autocorrelation has to be taken care of, before interpreting any possible results. The common instruments of choice are the Cochrane–Orcutt estimation method, where we unfortunately lose the first observation and the Prais–Winsten estimation, which does not have such a disadvantage and hence was taken. Unfortunately, the PW-estimation produced results that were far from satisfying, because the Adjusted R² values for both regressions became too small. A regression with an aR² of 0,872 resulted after the PW-Estimation in an aR² of 0,059 for Hamburg. For Saint Petersburg the aR² dropped from 0,446 to 0,329, which seemed less severe. Interestingly, a low Durbin Watson score might indicate a spurious regression. Every time I would correct for Autocorrelation, my explanatory power would drop to unsatisfying levels. I thought about this problem for weeks, performed hundreds of regressions and finally turned to the theory of the Wooldridge Book. After a while it became evident that stationarity, or better said non-stationarity sabotaged my results. I also confirmed that whether my Regression was measured in Euros or Ruble did not have any impact on the output tables besides scaling.³⁴

5.1.1. Stationarity

According to Wooldridge, stationarity assures that the variance and mean of a stochastic process does not change with time (in time-series). Unconditional joint probability distribution is for my econometric time-series analyses an underlying assumption that has to be fulfilled. The two most commonly used methods to test for stationarity are the “Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test for Unit Root” and the “Philips-Perron Unit Root Test”. The results of both tests can be seen in Table 1 below:

Variable	Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test for Unit Root	Philips-Perron Unit Root Test	Implication
HH_Haspax_J18	0,70	0,70	non-stationary
SPB_TurnoverOrg_J18E	0,71	0,50	non-stationary
HH_IndustProd_J18	0,65	0,53	non-stationary
SPB_IndustProd_J18E	0,68	0,74	non-stationary
HH_Salaries_J18	0,01	0,02	stationary
SPB_Salaries_J18E	0,01	0,01	stationary
HH_Constr_J18	0,01	0,01	stationary
SPB_Constr_J18E	0,01	0,01	stationary
HH_ServiceIndex	0,01	0,21	ambiguous
SPB_Services_J18E	0,51	0,18	non-stationary
HH_Unempl	0,48	0,68	non-stationary
SPB_Unempl	0,24	0,69	non-stationary

Table 1: Stationarity Results

Interestingly, we can see a very first finding when observing that it appears that always the same kind of variables are either stationary, or non-stationary. The only exception is the Service Index of Hamburg, which is ambiguous.

The easiest way to get rid of trends and transform a trending variable towards stationarity is simply to take the first difference to adjust for the mean and in persistent cases to take the second difference and thereby adjust for variance. In this specific case it was sufficient to take the first difference and all non-stationary results became stationary. Taking the first difference meant that I would lose one observation in the process. Nonetheless, even after differencing all non-stationary variables, my results were still unsatisfying. The explanatory power of my regressions was less than 4 percent. However, I was able to get rid of my serial correlation problem and did not depend on the PW-estimation anymore. Soon I realized after consultation with my supervisor that non-stationarity in independent variables was not a problem, but that I only needed to difference the dependent side of the regression. Thereafter I did not have any serial correlation problems and the Durbin-Watson tests showed no first-order autocorrelation anymore, while maintaining satisfying adjusted R^2 levels of approximately 0,363 for Saint Petersburg and 0,137 for Hamburg. I knew that adding seasonal dummies and lags would enhance these values later on. Later it turned out that adding lags and dummies resulted in negative autocorrelation and I had to rely once more on the Prais-Winsten-Estimation.

5.1.2. Curve Estimation and Dummies

When reflecting on the developments of the observed variables that were described thoroughly in Chapter 4.2., it becomes evident that seasonal effects might be present. While most Hamburg variables besides Construction seem to behave robust towards seasonality, many economic indicators in Saint Petersburg visually seem to experience stronger seasonal patterns. Additionally suspicious seems that even the dependent variable “Turnover of Organizations” might be subject to seasonal patterns, as we occasionally observe a rise in turnover towards the end of a given year and a drop in less important January. This gives us enough evidence to experiment with different forms of time-dummies.

Overall, there were three different types of dummies tested to increase model precision:

The first variant was a simple month dummy, where each month was simply coded by the month’s numeric counterpart. For example, February of each year would bare a 2. The second variant was a more clustering form, where each year would be divided into the four seasons. This dummy would always have a value of 2 for the months April, May and June. The third variant would simply chronologically count each month from 1 to 84, if the time-span included 84 observations. Basically, this number would simply correspond to the N-count.

All three variants were tested against each other in random combinations with the intuitive form of the models and checked for significance by Linear Regression Modelling in SPSS. The results were not really surprising. The seasonal dummy performed a little worse than the monthly

dummy. Most likely, because they are actually equivalents and differ only in graduation. The best performer turned out to be the chronological N dummy, which was also expected. Further analysis included also the N^2 and N^3 dummies and especially the N^3 dummy seemed promising. To prevent a spurious regression, we have to also keep the lower-order dummies, except for cases where we can explicitly regard a specific lower order dummy to be redundant. This means that if we include the dummy N^3 , we usually also have to include N^2 and N .

Extending the analysis to curve estimation, where the dependent variable is plotted against N with various possible curves including Linear, Logarithmic, Inverse, Quadratic, Cubic, Growth and Exponential, the cubic time trend turned out to be the most fitting.

Figure 36: Curve Estimation Saint Petersburg

Figure 37: Curve Estimation Hamburg

Figures 36 and 37 illustrate the curve fit of the dependent variable against the different possibilities. Interestingly, the adjusted R^2 for both scenarios was the highest for the cubic time-trend. The adjusted R^2 for the cubic fit in Hamburg amounts to 0,891. For Saint Petersburg the cubic fit equals to 0,523. This implies that both local economies might experience similar inflationary trends, probably rooted in the global economy. These time-trends include essentially the omitted variables, which are associated with the geometric economic development aside from the already observed variables.

All this leads to the conclusion that a time-variable should be included in the model and that this variable should bear the form N^3 . Therefore, N and N^2 are also to be included. In sum, we end up the $N^3 + N^2 + N$ representing time-developments with all the hidden forces that accompany time.

5.1.3. Lag Analysis

Now that we identified a suiting time variable, our models look like this:

Saint Petersburg:

$$SPB_TurnoverOrg_{j18E}' = IndustProd_{j18E} + Salaries_{j18E} + Constr_{j18E} + Services_{j18E} + Unempl + N + N^2 + N^3 + u$$

Hamburg:

$$HH_Haspax_{j18}' = IndustProd_{j18} + Salaries_{j18} + Constr_{j18} + ServiceIndex + Unempl + N + N^2 + N^3 + u$$

In the next step, we want now to bootstrap the two models in an iterative process by including all kinds of thinkable lags and select for the most relevant ones. Our objective here is to enhance the explanatory power of the resulting regression and reduce residuals. The instrument for evaluating whether a model-iteration is superior, or inferior is the Root Squared Mean Error (RMSE) and the Mean Absolute Error (MAE). We optimize for a lower value. Compellingly, most of the time, when the residuals of a regression dealt were processed with a significantly lower RMSE, usually (with very little exceptions) also the MAE was significantly smaller and the adjusted R^2 higher. In a way, the RMSE became the most telling evaluator.

Lags from 1 to 24 for all variables were tested, but it became clear very fast that the cost of including large lags was inappropriately high and decreased the sample size from an already questionably low number. Here, I would argue that for a larger sample size, maybe different lags would be more appropriate, but in the end the lags that were the most telling and most beneficial in my sample were somewhere between 1 and 3 months, depending on the variable.

Furthermore, I also experimented with lags of the dependent variables and they did indeed increase model predictability significantly. An AR(1) model might actually be a good choice, but including lags of the Y variable would violate Assumption TS3' (see next section). Thus, analysis of Y-lags was from thereon excluded and only possible X-variable lags were considered.

After performing hundreds of regressions (each lag combination required an own regression, consideration and RMSE-excel calculation), the following lags appeared to be the most relevant:

Saint Petersburg_Best Model:

SPB_Turnover_Organizations' =

ConstructionL1 + IndustrialProduction + IndustrialProductionL1 + Services + ServicesL1 +

Unemployment + UnemploymentL1 + UnemploymentL2 + SalariesL1 + N + N² + N³ + C

N=70. Adjusted R²=0,611. DW=2,020. RMSE=1,534 bln. EUR. MAE=1,067 bln. EUR.

Hamburg_Best Model:

HaspaxIndex' = **ConstructionL3 + IndustrialProductionL2 + Services + Unemployment +
UnemploymentL2 + UnemploymentL3 + Salaries + N + N² + N³ + C**

N=81. Adjusted R²=0,446. DW=2,235. RMSE=149,60 Index Points. MAE=109,37 Index Points.

5.2. Econometric Assumption Testing

As described in the Woodridge study book chapter 11, we should make sure that certain assumptions are fulfilled before we can even try to interpret the results of a regression. In this sub-chapter I want to investigate all necessary econometric conditions to insure asymptotic properties and show that the results are indeed worth searching narratives for. This will be done for both optimized models at question, namely Hamburg_Best and Saint Petersburg_Best.

The Asymptotic Gauss-Markov assumptions for time-series include:

1. Assumption TS.1' (Linearity and Weak Dependence)
2. Assumption TS.2' (No Perfect Collinearity)
3. Assumption TS.3' (Zero Conditional Mean)
4. Assumption TS.4' (Homoskedasticity)
5. Assumption TS.5' (No Serial Correlation)

5.2.1. Assumption Testing Hamburg_Best Model

The optimized Hamburg_Best model consists of 81 considered observations. 3 observations were lost due to lags to the order of 3. Initially, the total observation set consisted of 84 observations. In optimized form the Hamburg_Best model has the following structure:

$$\text{HaspaxIndex}' = \text{ConstructionL3} + \text{IndustrialProductionL2} + \text{Services} + \text{Unemployment} + \text{UnemploymentL2} + \text{UnemploymentL3} + \text{Salaries} + N + N^2 + N^3 + C$$

N=81. Adjusted R²=0,446. DW=2,235. RMSE=149,60 Index Points. MAE=109,37 Index Points.

All bold variables are significant at least at the 10-percent level in the final regression.

Assumption TS.1' (Linearity and Weak Dependence)

Linearity:

It is easy to see that the model is linear in parameters. The only component that might be at question is N, N² and N³, but in the end N is simply a numeric fixed number and does not infringe the linearity characteristics.

Weak Dependence:

Weak dependence is a little harder to argue, because the idea itself is more abstract. In essence we have to make sure that correlation of X(t) and X(t) + H goes towards zero sufficiently quickly as time strives for infinity. Thereby the error dies out and the results become consistent. In principle, one way of showing a behavior where the error shows a trend to die out might be by looking at the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the error terms.

Figure 38: ACF Plot of Residuals in Hamburg_Best Model

Figure 38 is my best attempt to visually show a rapidly declining correlation of u-correlations as time progresses. It does not reach zero in within the observation-span, but implies a sufficiently rapid

decline, which in term would suggest a weak dependence. Hence an OLS-regression would be asymptotically consistent.

Assumption TS.2' (No Perfect Collinearity)

In order to investigate the collinearity of the regressors, we can look into the Variance Inflation Factor-Statistics (VIF) output-table of SPSS. In an optimal case we would strive for a value of below 10, which in turn would be equivalent to a collinearity tolerance of 0,10. Dividing 1 by the VIF-Statistics equals the corresponding collinearity tolerance. In our specific case, however, we only need to make sure that we have no “perfect collinearity”, which means that the statistics should not be infinite and the tolerance not be absolute zero.

Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	HHConst18L3	,690	1,450
	HHIndustPr18L2	,242	4,129
	Service Index HH	,394	2,539
	HH Unemployment	,133	7,523
	HH Salaries Jan18	,138	7,249
	CountMonths	,005	215,181
	CountMonthsSquared	,001	1347,015
	CountMonthsCubic	,002	549,057
	HHUnemplL2	,049	20,299
	HHUnemplL3	,060	16,687

a. Dependent Variable: DIFF
(HH_HaspaxIndex_Jan18,1)

Table 2: VIF-Statistics Hamburg_Best Model

In Table 2, we see that we have no case of perfect collinearity. Adding additional lags of a variable obviously increases collinearity. Furthermore, the dummies N , N^2 and N^3 are very strongly collinear, but by no means perfectly collinear.

At this point, we can conclude that we have no case of perfect collinearity and therefore Assumption TS.2' is not compromised.

Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	HHConst18L3	,706	1,416
	HHIndustPr18L2	,464	2,157
	Service Index HH	,537	1,862
	HH Unemployment	,146	6,840
	HH Salaries Jan18	,143	6,969
	CountMonths	,116	8,592
	HHUnemplL2	,051	19,656
	HHUnemplL3	,062	16,179

a. Dependent Variable: DIFF
(HH_HaspaxIndex_Jan18,1)

Table 3: VIF-Statistics after removing N^2 and N^3

Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	HHConst18L3	,720	1,389
	HHIndustPr18L2	,511	1,957
	Service Index HH	,542	1,845
	HH Unemployment	,161	6,209
	HH Salaries Jan18	,149	6,691
	CountMonths	,123	8,144
	HHUnemplL3	,244	4,096

a. Dependent Variable: DIFF
(HH_HaspaxIndex_Jan18,1)

Table 4: VIF-Statistics after removing N^2 , N^3 and Unemployment Lag 2.

In Table 3 we can observe how the VIF-Statistics changes after removing the time-dummies N^2 and N^3 , which have extraordinary strong collinearity. Removing thereafter also Unemployment Lag 2, which has the highest remaining value results in Table 4. In Table 4 we can see that all collinearity tolerances are above 0,10 and all VIF-Values are below 10. Nonetheless, we need not to go such a step as even strong collinearity does not violate Assumption TS.2'.

Assumption TS.3' (Zero Conditional Mean)

The next assumption at question for a successful interpretation of results is the assumption of Zero Conditional Mean. I want to show that a change in X does not lead to a change in mean of the residuals along the axis.

Figure 39: Residual Plot of HH_Best Model

AVG 1 - 20	- 0,89
AVG 21 - 40	3,98
AVG 41 - 60	- 8,21
AVG 61 - 80	6,77
AVG 1 - 40	1,54
AVG 41 - 81	- 1,24

Table 5: Clustered averages of Residuals in HH_Best Model.

Figure 39 is a plot of the Residuals of the Hamburg_Best Model along the chronological observation order. Throughout the time-span, we have an $E(u)=0,08$. This is not exactly zero, but considerably close. What stands out are the three big spikes at $X=\{60; 62; 79\}$. These three outliers are, nevertheless, not sufficient to talk of an inflation of Residuals along the time axis, because the non-outliers, which dominate the observation quantitatively do not seem to experience an inflationary pattern. Moreover, if clustering observations into

comparable periods (see Table 5), we arguably see that averages are more similar than dissimilar (at least in magnitude). Consequently, we can reason that Assumption TS.3' is sufficiently satisfied to continue the analysis.

Assumption TS.4' (Homoskedasticity)

The next assumption to be verified is TS.4' that requires the errors to be contemporaneously homoscedastic. Figure 40 is a Heteroskedasticity Plot, where the Predicted values are plotted against the Residual Values. Due to the fact that it is not always easy to visually see if clustering is sufficient to talk of heteroskedasticity, we should additionally test for heteroskedasticity with help of further instruments for confirmation.

Figure 40: Heteroskedasticity Plot of HH_Best.

Generally speaking, there are three tests that are most commonly used to test for heteroskedasticity. They are the “Breusch-Pagan Test”, the “modified Breusch-Pagan Test” and “White’s Test” for heteroskedasticity. Which test to use depends mostly on the error-distribution. If errors are normally distributed, we should trust the Breusch-Pagan Test. If the errors are rather normally distributed, but kurtosis particularly high, or low we should appeal to the modified Breusch-Pagan Test. In case of a non-standard distribution, White’s Test should be the most telling. As illustrated in Figure 41, we can see a rather normal distribution of errors, but kurtosis is extraordinarily high and hence we should trust the modified Breusch-Pagan Test in our specific case. At a p-value of 0,172 we fail to reject the 0-Hypothesis (H_1 confirms heteroskedasticity) and can thus assume homoskedasticity.³⁵

→ Graph

Modified Breusch-Pagan Test for Heteroskedasticity^{a,b,c}

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
1,868	1	,172

- a. Dependent variable: DIFF (HH_HaspaxIndex_Jan18,1)
- b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.
- c. Predicted values from design: Intercept + HHConst18L3 + HHIndustPr18L2 + HH_Services + HH_Unemployment + HHUnemplL2 + HHUnemplL3 + HHSalariesJan18 + CountMonths + ...

Table 6: Modified Breusch-Pagan Test of HH_Best.

Figure 41: Residual Histogram of HH_Best Model

Breusch-Pagan Test for Heteroskedasticity ^{a,b,c}		
Chi-Square	df	Sig.
3,101	1	,078

Table 7: Breusch-Pagan Test HH_Best.

White Test for Heteroskedasticity ^{a,b,c}		
Chi-Square	df	Sig.
71,331	49	,020

Table 8: White's Test HH_Best.

Interestingly, both alternative tests might imply heteroskedasticity. At this point it might be relevant to underline that we use the Prais-Winsten estimation. The Prais-Winsten estimation is a Feasible General Least Squares (fGLS), which means that the instrument corrects for heteroskedasticity anyways. Overall, the instrument of choice, the modified Breusch-Pagan Test suggests the absence of heteroskedasticity.

Assumption TS.5' (No Serial Correlation)

The problem of autocorrelation was one of the key-problems in the data-investigation that led to the utilization of the Prais-Winsten estimation. Adding additional variables to an existing regression iteratively spins autocorrelation positively and negatively arbitrarily. Therefore, correcting for serial correlation was inevitable. After 3 iterations, we end up with a Durbin Watson statistic of 2,135. This means that we have no issue with serial correlation left and can regard Assumption TS.5' as fulfilled.

In addition, in the fundamental Gauss-Markov Assumptions we usually also test for TS6, normality. Although there is no such assumption in the asymptotic version, we can easily confirm as was visible in Figure 41 that we have a rather normal distribution of errors, but a high kurtosis. Moreover, we know that White's Test doesn't only test for heteroskedasticity, but also might indicate a specification error. Due to the fact that we have no cross-sectional product term in the equation, we can neglect such possibility.

In summary we have shown that none of the examined assumptions was violated. Therefore, we can conclude that the regression-results for the Hamburg_Best model are indeed interpretable.

5.2.2. Assumption Testing Saint Petersburg_Best Model

In this subsection we will repeat the same procedure in verifying all necessary assumptions that would allow us to interpret the results of the Saint Petersburg_Best model. The chain of argumentation will, however, be kept shorter due to parallelism to the corresponding analysis for the Hamburg_Best model.

The Saint Petersburg_Best model bears the following form:

SPB_Turnover_Organizations' =

ConstructionL1 + IndustrialProduction + IndustrialProductionL1 + Services + ServicesL1 + Unemployment + UnemploymentL1 + UnemploymentL2 + SalariesL1 + N + N² + N³ + C

N=70. Adjusted R²=0,611. DW=2,020. RMSE=1,534 bln. EUR. MAE=1,067 bln. EUR.

Just as in the Hamburg equivalent, all bold variables are significant at the 10-percent level. Moreover, we encounter here some form of an anomaly. N² is included into the equation, but gets cancelled out by performing the Prais-Winsten estimation. I will try to explain this later on.

Assumption TS.1' (Linearity and Weak Dependence)

Linearity:

The argumentation is basically the same as for the Hamburg_Best model. The model is linear in parameters and only the dummies N² and N³ might have non-linear tendencies, but do not infringe the linearity assumption due to their numerical essence.

Weak Dependence:

Figure 42: ACF Plot of Saint Petersburg_Best residuals.

Just as has been argued in the Hamburg model, it visually appears in Figure 42, as well that the autocorrelation of errors dies out rather quickly and appears to eventually reach zero in a longer observation span. This suggests weak dependence.

Assumption TS.2' (No Perfect Collinearity)

Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	SPB_Const_EUR18_L1	,458	2,185
	SPB Industrial Production Jan18 EUR	,023	44,186
	SPB_InstrProd_EUR18_L1	,017	58,254
	SPB_Services_SPB Jan18 EUR	,196	5,115
	SPB_Services_EUR18_L1	,099	10,067
	SPB Unemployment	,022	46,196
	SPB_Unemployment_L1	,011	89,990
	SPB_Unemployment_L2	,028	35,629
	SPB_Salaries_EUR18_L1	,214	4,663
	CountMonths	,000	2604,883
	CountMonthsSquarred	,000	8301,451
	CountMonthsCubic	,000	2059,758

a. Dependent Variable: SPB Turnover Organizations Jan18 EUR

Just as in the case of Hamburg, we see very strong collinearity in N , N^2 , N^3 . The VIF statistics for N^2 especially are extraordinarily high and might indeed be the reason why N^2 gets cancelled out during the Prais-Winsten iterations. Furthermore, far more lags turned out to be of relevance and thus we can see greater overall collinearity. Besides the N^2 , which is extraordinarily high, we can see no perfect collinearity.

Table 9: VIF Statistics Saint Petersburg_Best model.

Assumption TS.3' (Zero Conditional Mean)

Arguing that the Zero Conditional Mean assumption is fulfilled in this model is a little tricky due to $E(u)=5$ million. Nonetheless, we have to relativize this value to the appropriate scale. In face of spikes that occasionally touch the 3 000 million marks, a value of merely 5 million would in relative terms be 0,17 percent of such a vast scale. Therefore, although the value seems unjustifiably large on first sight, it is actually pretty close to $E(u)=0$ in relative terms.

Figure 43: Residual Plot of the Saint Petersburg_Best model.

$E(u) =$	4.667.957
AVG 1- 20	- 241.286.940
AVG 21 - 40	272.188.500
AVG 41 - 60	38.025.010
AVG 1 - 35	97.917.279
AVG 36 - 70	- 88.581.365

Table 10: Part-Expectations of Residuals in the Saint Petersburg_Best model.

Figure 43 describes the calculated residuals along the observation span and it does appear that the positive spikes are larger in magnitude compare to the negative spikes. Nevertheless, the spikes seem to be distributed non-systematically and we cannot say that there are higher chances of large deviations in early or late observations. Table 10 shows the averages of residual-values in specific parts of the observationspan. We do not observe implications that the conditional mean would be non-zero in relative terms.

Assumption TS.4' (Homoskedasticity)

The verification of the homoskedasticity assumption is a little puzzling as well, because the plot connecting fitted values and residuals does visually look like being subject to clustering around the central area as can be seen in Figure 45. A possible heteroskedasticity would not infringe the validity of the regression anyways, because a the Prais-Winsten fGLS does correct for heteroskedasticity.

Figure 44: Histogram of Saint Petersburg_Best Residuals.

Figure 45: Heteroskedasticity Plot Saint Petersburg_Best model.

For the sake of completion, we still would like to find out if we indeed have heteroskedasticity or not. As can be seen in Figure 44, the residual histogram is rather normally distributed. We do have a slightly high kurtosis, but I would argue that the distribution is rather absolutely normally distributed and would suggest to use the standard Breusch-Pagan test as instrument for confirmation. Furthermore, we can also argue that the observation number at N=70 is rather low and the reason for small roughness of the histogram. The Breusch-Pagan test in Table 11 suggests that the H_0 assumption of homoskedasticity cannot be rejected and that we do have indeed homoskedasticity. Interestingly the alternative tests suggest the same interpretation despite the fact that heteroskedasticity seems visible in Figure 45.

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
2,088	1	,148

- a. Dependent variable: DIFF (SPB_TurnoverOrganizations_Jan18_EUR,1)
- b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.
- c. Predicted values from design: Intercept + SPB_Const_EUR18_L1 + SPB_IndustrialProduction_Jan18_EUR + SPB_InstrProd_EUR18_L1 + SPB_Services_EUR18_L1 + SPB_Unemployment + SPB_Unemployment_L1 + SPB_Unemployment_L2 + SPB_Salaries_EUR18_L1 + CountMonths + ...

Table 11: Breusch-Pagan Test Saint Petersburg_Best model.

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
1,057	1	,304

- a. Dependent variable: DIFF (SPB_TurnoverOrganizations_Jan18_EUR,1)
- b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.
- c. Predicted values from design: Intercept + SPB_Const_EUR18_L1 + SPB_IndustrialProduction_Jan18_EUR + SPB_InstrProd_EUR18_L1 + SPB_Services_EUR18_L1 + SPB_Unemployment + SPB_Unemployment_L1 + SPB_Unemployment_L2 + SPB_Salaries_EUR18_L1 + CountMonths + ...

Table 12: Modified Breusch-Pagan Saint Petersburg_Best model.

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
64,305	61	,362

- a. Dependent variable: DIFF (SPB_TurnoverOrganizations_Jan18_EUR,1)
- b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.

Table 13: White Test Saint Petersburg_Best model.

Assumption TS.5' (No Serial Correlation)

The final assumption TS.5' is also satisfied as the Durbin-Watson index of 2,020 as a result of the fGLS Prais-Winsten estimation corrected for possible autocorrelation anyways. The additional question about normality of distribution can also be answered as fulfilled as the histogram in Figure 44 indicates a normal distribution of errors with a neglectable slightly high kurtosis.

In Summary we can say that all necessary assumptions seem to be fulfilled and that the results of the Saint Petersburg_Best model can, just as the results of the Hamburg_Best model interpreted with increased confidence.

6. Results and Interpretation

In this section, we will finally explore the results of the two optimized models Hamburg_Best and Saint Petersburg_Best. We will also try to come up with logical narratives for the results and their possible interpretations.

6.1. Results Hamburg

Table 14 below shows the results of the Hamburg_Best model. The regression was performed by the Prais-Winsten fGLS Estimation in 3 iterations. Most regressors are significant, because a regressor, which by inclusion reduces RMSE and increases adjusted R² is usually also significant. An exception is for example the second lag of industrial production, which deals with both advantages even without being significant. The model has an RMSE of 149,60 index points and an N of 81. MAE is equal to 109,37 index points. The dependent variable is the first difference of the for inflation adjusted HASPAX Index, meaning the growth rate. Due to a rather small N, I would perceive any significance at the 10-percent level as significant, although all significant variables in Table 14 also reach the 5 percent threshold. In the next step, we will try to interpret the results of Table 14.

Regression Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
HHConst18L3	-1,469E-6	,000	-,225	-2,050	,044
HHIndustPr18L2	-2,741E-8	,000	-,131	-,685	,495
Service Index HH	3,498	1,025	,500	3,411	,001
HH Unemployment	,021	,006	,939	3,481	,001
HHUnemplL2	-,050	,011	-2,211	-4,673	,000
HHUnemplL3	,038	,009	1,694	4,064	,000
HH Salaries Jan18	1,012	,477	,530	2,122	,037
CountMonths	-12,547	9,499	-1,759	-1,321	,191
CountMonthsSquarred	,393	,263	4,978	1,493	,140
CountMonthsCubic	-,003	,002	-3,392	-1,590	,116
(Constant)	-4902,968	2165,972		-2,264	,027

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

Table 14: Result table of Hamburg_Best model regression.

Final Iteration 3

Autocorrelation Coefficient

Rho (AR1)	Std. Error
-,213	,118

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

Model Fit Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
,668	,446	,358	162,088	2,135

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Regression	1460419,443	10	146041,944
Residual	1812809,121	69	26272,596

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

Table 15: Additional Output parameters of Hamburg_Best model.

The first significant predictor of economic growth to discuss is Construction three months ago at $p=0,044^{**}$. The impact is surprisingly negative meaning that every Euro paid to the construction industry 3 months ago tends to decrease Index Growth by 0,00000147 index points. Scaling to an 1 000 000 EUR increase in construction turnover would lead to a loss of 1,47 index points in growth rate of the HASPAX index. This would make in so far sense that money that was invested in construction cannot be spent elsewhere and constructing a building, especially in democratic Germany might take a very long time before making any significant positive impact. Industrial production is unfortunately insignificant, and would intuitively be one of the key indicators for a healthy economy. This is unexpected, as the industry is a vital driver for any developing economy according to conventional wisdom. Additional research on why industrial production didn't turn out as a good indicator might be an interesting task. Reasons might involve a low observation number or the possibility that the HASPAX-Index doesn't capture all the economic fluctuations.

The next variable at question is the service index. It is significant at the 99,9-percent level. Every increase in service-turnover by 1 index-point is immediately associated with an increase of HASPAX Index growth of 3,5 basis points. This would make insofar sense, as turnover gained through provision of services is fast-usable income. The service provider could spend the earned money the very next day and does not have to invest in industrial-machinery in most cases.

Unemployment-rate is a little tricky to explain, because all of the lags are highly significant at the 99-percent threshold. Furthermore, we observe an alternate in their impact-direction. Unemployment, Unemployment Lag 2 and Unemployment Lag 3 experience a +-+ trend, maybe resembling a sinus/co-sinus pattern. An intuitive narrative might hence be susceptible to Ockham's Razor. Moreover, the individual impact moments seem to have a very large magnitude compared to other variables. To be exact, an increase in unemployment rate 3 months ago by

1 000 people leads to a HASPAX-Index growth of 38 basis points. An increase of the unemployment rate 2 months ago by 1 000 people decreases this periods Index growth by 50 basis points. And additional 1 000 unemployed people in this month once again lead to a positive impact of 21 basis points. This finding might suggest that we have to weigh the impact of all periods against each other to come to a more modest total impact. Calculating just the three moments at discussion would interestingly already lead to a total impact of $+38 -50 + 21 = +9$, which is taken together already far more convincing than trying to explain a negative impact as large as 50. This raises also the question, if other variables might experience similar effects. One possible narrative to sell this finding might be to argue that 1 000 people lost their jobs today. They were a burden for their companies and got fired out of necessity. This benefited their companies by 38 basis Points growth in the HASPAX-Index immediately. Two months later, they became a burden to society, do not produce anything and consume only little. They cost the economy 50 index-points in possible growth and live off, and drain social welfare. Then 3 months (one season) after their job-loss some of them begin to fill structurally important, maybe critical positions in other structurally fractioned spheres and thus boost economic growth by 21 basis points on average. It is likely that their impact does not only affect the three regarded months, but that all months together can be summed to some absolute impact. There is, however, little sense in including additional lags of unemployment to the shown model. This is at least my attempt to explain what I see. It is likely that other, diverging explanations are more convincing.

The next covariate to discuss is salary level, which is significant at $p=0,037^{**}$. For every increase of average salary level by 1 Euro in the current period, we can expect a boost to economic output growth by 1,012 basis points. This might suggest that Hamburg employees can be motivated to increase economic output in the short run quite strongly by offering additional salary.

Interestingly, all seasonal dummies are insignificant, although some seasonal effects would usually be expected. And the used dummies are already the most efficient of the ones tested. The HASPAX-Index itself does indeed not look like it has seasonal patterns. Merely some of the independent variables that we use to predict economic development do. This speaks actually for robustness and economic stability of the Hamburg economy, which we already witnessed in the data examination section. The same cannot be said of the Saint Petersburg data, as we will discuss later on.

The only remaining part of the output table to be interpreted is the significant constant at $p=0,027^{**}$, with an unstandardized value of - 4 902. This suggests that the HASPAX-Index would basically implode within one to two periods, if all variables were to go towards zero. The HASPAX Index Stood at 6 501 basis points in December 2021. If all would go to zero, the index would collapse before we would reach the second period. This might actually be inherited from the

financial nature of the index making it susceptible to financial pressures and ease of liquidity by shareholders.

6.1.1. Addition Consideration for the Hamburg N=70 case

Due to the fact that the Hamburg_Best model investigates 81 observations (after losing 3 observations to lag-inclusion), it becomes important to know if results were significantly different if the Hamburg model would also deal with only 70 observations, as is the case for the Saint Petersburg_Best model. If results were to differ substantially, then the Hamburg analysis should also include only 70 observations to keep both models as comparable as possible. Subsequently I would like to discuss the same regression with only 70 observations for Hamburg.

Regression Coefficients					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
HHConst18L3	-1,630E-6	,000	-,247	-2,190	,033
HHIndustPr18L2	-1,566E-8	,000	-,079	-,307	,760
Service Index HH	3,651	,993	,551	3,675	,001
HH Unemployment	,026	,006	1,211	4,148	,000
HHUnemplL2	-,053	,011	-2,511	-4,911	,000
HHUnemplL3	,038	,009	1,801	4,028	,000
HH Salaries Jan18	1,254	,513	,579	2,444	,018
CountMonths	-21,166	28,081	-2,542	-,754	,454
CountMonthsSquarred	,552	,671	6,668	,822	,414
CountMonthsCubic	-,004	,005	-4,412	-,901	,371
(Constant)	-5925,106	2290,957		-2,586	,012

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

Table 16: Hamburg_Best Regression Output with N=70. RMSE=147,99; MAE=109,05; $aR^2=0,427$

Regression Coefficients					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
HHConst18L3	-1,469E-6	,000	-,225	-2,050	,044
HHIndustPr18L2	-2,741E-8	,000	-,131	-,685	,495
Service Index HH	3,498	1,025	,500	3,411	,001
HH Unemployment	,021	,006	,939	3,481	,001
HHUnemplL2	-,050	,011	-2,211	-4,673	,000
HHUnemplL3	,038	,009	1,694	4,064	,000
HH Salaries Jan18	1,012	,477	,530	2,122	,037
CountMonths	-12,547	9,499	-1,759	-1,321	,191
CountMonthsSquarred	,393	,263	4,978	1,493	,140
CountMonthsCubic	-,003	,002	-3,392	-1,590	,116
(Constant)	-4902,968	2165,972		-2,264	,027

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

Table 14 (repeat): Result table of Hamburg_Best model regression. N=83. RMSE=149,60; MAE=109,37; $aR^2=0,358$

Table 16 shows the output for the case that only the 70 most recent observations for Hamburg are considered. Table 14 is a repost to show both output tables side-by-side and convey their similarities most easily. We can see that both regressions are very similar. The same variables are significant for both cases. The unstandardized B's for all variables are very close to each other. We do have more diverging, but neglectable differences in the significance and impact of the anyhow insignificant seasonal dummies. Besides that, the constant gaps by approx. 20 percent. All those differences are mostly irrelevant. We do, however, also see a 25 percent difference in the unstandardized impact of the variable "HH Salaries Jan18". The standardized coefficient differs on the other hand by merely a little over 9 percent. Overall, it is evident that the results would be almost absolutely identical if we were to only tolerate 70 observations. Consequently, it is favorable to use the more precise results originating from including as many time-points as we possibly can. Comparing Hamburg with N=81 to Saint Petersburg with N=70 seems justifiable at this point.

6.1.2. Heuristic Equivalent of Index Points

A key challenge of comparing both result-outcomes against each other is the difference in units of outcome. For Saint Petersburg, we have impacts measured in Euros, but for Hamburg impacts measured in Index Points. Essentially, we have now to compare pears with apples. A very heuristic and simplified approach might be to find a conversion rate and simply convert index points to Euros. This requires the very strong assumption that index point changes behave similar in nature, as turnover of companies. An assumption that was necessary throughout this whole thesis. According to the “Statistisches Bundesamt”, the total turnover of companies in Hamburg that had a turnover of above 22 000 Euros in 2020 managed to generate a total turnover of approximately 375,49 billion Euros. With this turnover, the Hamburg companies managed to boost the HASPAX Index towards 5 047,17 basis points in December 2020. Very heuristically speaking, the reached 5 047,17 basis points are a representation of the 375,49 billion Euros in turnover. If an equivalence can truly be argued, then 1 index point would represent 74,40 million Euros.

As a side-note, the aggregated turnover of Saint Petersburg companies in 2020 amounted to 170,22 billion Euros, which is approximately 45,33 percent of Hamburg’s turnover in 2020 while having 297 percent the population-size (5,5 million vs. 1,85 million). The per capita turnover of companies in Saint Petersburg would thus have an equivalent of 15,26 percent in terms of Hamburg effectivity per capita. By implication this would mean that in Hamburg, every citizen would account for 6,55 times the turnover, which was observed in Saint Petersburg. I want to underline that this oversimplified calculation has so many underlying assumptions that it should be taken with utmost caution. The dynamics of Hamburg’s economy would certainly be different if the population would be 3 times as large. Interestingly, this rate would change only slightly if we were to compare the working population of 3 million in Saint Petersburg versus 1 million in Hamburg.

	B (unstandardized Coefficient)	Std. Error	p
HHConst18L3	- 109,28 €	53,29 €	0,04
HHIndustPr18L2	- 2,04 €	2,98 €	0,50
Service Index HH	260.228.355,47 €	76.284.062,53 €	0,00
HH Unemployment	1.576.590,91 €	452.900,92 €	0,00
HHUnemplL2	- 3.703.959,20 €	792.674,52 €	0,00
HHUnemplL3	2.834.681,16 €	697.462,31 €	0,00
HH Salaries Jan18	75.324.214,78 €	35.499.406,07 €	0,04
CountMonths	- 933.437.552,68 €	706.725.749,04 €	0,19
CountMonthsSquared	29.213.198,84 €	19.571.703,26 €	0,14
CountMonthsCubic	- 245.513,82 €	154.441,76 €	0,12
(Constant)	- 364.761.899.953,78 €	161.139.971.693,00 €	0,03

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

Table 17: Results Table of Hamburg_Best Model, if converting Index Points to Euros at rate: 1 to 74.396.146,75 €

Table 17 illustrates the same results as Table 14, if the index points are heuristically converted to Euros under strong assumptions. The interpretation is analogous as in section 6.1.

6.2. Results Saint Petersburg

Below we can see the results of the Saint Petersburg_Best model regression in Table 17. One substantial difference to the Hamburg results is that the value of accounting is not growth in index points, but growth of turnover of companies located in Saint Petersburg in Euros.

Regression Coefficients					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
SPB_Const_EUR18_L1	1,481	,593	,250	2,497	,015
SPB Industrial Production Jan18 EUR	,958	,456	1,524	2,102	,040
SPB_InstrProd_EUR18_L1	-,015	,006	-1,817	-2,413	,019
Services SPB Jan18 EUR	17,245	7,072	,512	2,439	,018
SPB_Services_EUR18_L1	-22,041	9,135	-,646	-2,413	,019
SPB Unemployment	-92715,508	48790,958	-1,413	-1,900	,062
SPB_Unemployment_L1	138150,603	79511,723	2,108	1,737	,088
SPB_Unemployment_L2	-61550,347	43401,932	-,941	-1,418	,162
SPB_Salaries_EUR18_L1	-12204947,642	4594025,895	-,504	-2,657	,010
CountMonths	-24190389,582	68514598,393	-,254	-,353	,725
CountMonthsCubic	9164,852	5423,201	,817	1,690	,097
(Constant)	13288340373	5087859189,9		2,612	,011

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

Table 18: Results table Saint Petersburg_Best Model. N=70; RMSE=1,534 bln. EUR; MAE=1,067 bln. EUR

Compared to the Hamburg_Best model, we have a higher number of included lags, which turned out to significantly impact model precision positively. The tradeoff-price being more collinearity among independent variables. In general, we can say that we can see the association of various economic variables to the first difference of economic output.

Interpreting the results table chronologically, construction spending of last month is the first significant predictor for economic growth at $p=0,02^{**}$. We can say that every Euro spend on construction last month increases economic output of this month by an average of 1,5 Euros. It would be tempting to prematurely conclude that construction spending would be great, because it leads to a multiplier of 1,5 in growth acceleration. Such a conclusion would be misleading, because we already saw in the investigation of unemployment in the Hamburg model that we would need to aggregate the impact of all months against each other and find this way the aggregated impact curve of all previous construction months. Nonetheless, we can say that a rise in construction-turnover tends to increase economic growth in the consecutive month. Identical arguments can be made for all following variables at question.

Contrary to the case of Hamburg, industrial production in Saint Petersburg does indeed have significant impacts on economic turnover-growth of Saint Petersburg companies. Both, the current month's industrial production ($p=0,04^{**}$) and previous month's industrial production ($p=0,02^{**}$) have significant effects on economic growth. According to the available data, the Saint Petersburg industry was declining for years and thus the negative results are not very

surprising. Last month's industrial production turnover decreases economic growth by 1,5 percent. Every Euro led this month through the industrial pipeline grows the economy by 0,96 Euros. This seems to be the reflection of the steady declining industrial sector, which discounts investments year-over-year. Slow, but steadily.

Coming to the service sector, we can again argue that two periods appear to be of relevance. The current period and the previous period, just as in industrial production. Each additional Euro spent in the service sector this month increases economic growth by 17,25 EUR in this month ($p=0,02^{**}$), but decreases economic growth next month by 22,04 EUR ($p=0,02^{**}$). One narrative might be that services are mostly performed to other service providers and this increases the speed at which that one Euro changes hands stimulating the economy, but leaves the next service-provider in the supply chain with a financial hole in the subsequent month. The overall net-effect of service-turnover seems to be negative within each two most recent periods.

Very surprisingly we see the same --+ pattern in unemployment, as we already observed in Hamburg, but in reverse (in Hamburg it was ++). This supports the hypothesis that impacts of unemployment fluctuations move in some kind of sinus-cosinus impact-curve. A possible narrative might look something like this:

1. In $t=0$, an employee becomes unemployed and in this very period, economic turnover-growth decreases by 93 000 EUR ($p=0,06^*$). The employee was most likely not fired due to his lack of skills, but due to the economic hardship of the company, which lacks investment. Inefficient employees survived in Russian culture since the Soviet Aera.
2. In the next period, the company is more efficient due to lack of the burdensome employee. The company makes an additional turnover of 138 000 EUR ($p=0,09^*$). Berdugo et al. (2008) already pointed out that mechanisms exist in which keeping ineffective employees slows down economic growth.³⁶

Such an observation appears, however, too simple to describe various positive and negative impacts, balancing each other resulting from firing employees, while not knowing the employee's type due to information asymmetry. As shown by the regression results, the impact can be good today, bad tomorrow and good the period after that, or the other way around. Common sense would suggest nevertheless that firing a burdensome employee should on average lead to an overall positive effect for the company.

3. The impact of the third period is insignificant ($p=0,16$), but on average the company experiences a loss of additional 61 500 EUR. Maybe the company takes at least two months to structurally adapt to the missing personnel.

Such a narrative makes little sense on first sight, because employees in Russia earn on average throughout the observation period merely 841,5 EUR per month. An employee being on average responsible for a turnover of 100-times his or her salary seems unrealistic. But we have to recall that we talk about “registered unemployed” and there is little incentive to brand oneself officially as jobless with the authorities, without social welfare expectations. Therefore, the “registered unemployed” should be seen as representers of maybe dozens of unemployed. Moreover, a self-selection bias might and most likely does exist. Nevertheless, the +- patterns appear interesting and might be worthy of further research.

Apparently, an increase in salary-level seems to have very significant negative effect on the growth-rate of turnover of Saint Petersburg companies. If average salary increases even by 1 Euro, on average this leads to a loss in economic turn-over growth of 12,2 million EUR ($p=0,01^{***}$). Such a statement requires certainly further explanation. According to KNOEMA, approximately 3 million out of the total population of Saint Petersburg (5,5 million total) belong to the working population. Basically, most people work, because as said so often before, Russia is not a welfare state and working is necessary for survival. This means that increasing the salary of 3 million employees by 1 EUR leads to a loss in economic growth of approx. 12 million EUR. This might imply a multiplier of 4x. In this case, it would make no economic sense to introduce a minimum-wage in Saint Petersburg, because such a change would factually have negative consequences for economic growth.

Coming to the seasonal Dummies, we can see that N is insignificant. N^2 was cancelled out by the iterative process of the Prais-Winsten Estimation, most likely due to the high collinearity as already argued in previous sections. N^3 on the other hand is slightly significant at $p=0,1^*$, meaning at the 10-percent level. This implies that economic growth in Saint Petersburg is really following a cubic time-trend.

The constant is also significant at $p=0,01^{***}$ and positive. This means that there is a fundamental difference compared to Hamburg, where the constant is negatively significant. In Hamburg, the financial index would theoretically implode in absence of variable-coefficients. In Saint Petersburg in contrast, the data suggests a positive growth rate in absence of all variables. A hypothesis might be that economic stimulation comes from somewhere untraced hinting to possible omitted variables like subsidies resulting from Oil/Gas sales on state-level that subsidies economic turnover. A further hypothesis might be that there is some fundamental growth, even when all observed variables go to zero. This would imply a systematic contrast of the real economy to a financial index, where market pressure rather diminishes growth in absence of positive stimuli and news.

7. Discussion

In this section I would like to address and discuss the results of the thesis by reflecting on contrasts and similarities of both city-level economies.

Hamburg	B (unstandardized Coefficient) in EUR	B (unstandardized Coefficient) in Index Points	p	Saint Petersburg	B (unstandardized Coefficient) in EUR	p
HHConst18L3	- 109,28 €	- 0,0000015	0,044	SPB_Const_EUR18_L1	1,48 €	0,015
HHIndustPr18L2	- 2,04 €	- 0,00000027	0,50	SPB_Industrial_Production_Jan18_EUR	0,96 €	0,040
Service Index HH	260.228.355,47 €	3,50	0,0011	SPB_InstrProd_EUR18_L1	- 0,02 €	0,019
HH Unemployment	1.576.590,91 €	0,021	0,00087	Services SPB Jan18 EUR	17,24 €	0,018
HHUnempl2	- 3.703.959,20 €	- 0,050	0,000014	SPB_Services_EUR18_L1	- 22,04 €	0,019
HHUnempl3	2.834.681,16 €	0,038	0,00013	SPB Unemployment	- 92.715,51 €	0,062
HH Salaries Jan18	75.324.214,78 €	1,012	0,037	SPB_Unemployment_L1	138.150,60 €	0,088
CountMonths	- 933.437.552,68 €	- 12,55	0,19	SPB_Unemployment_L2	- 61.550,35 €	0,16
CountMonthsSquarred	29.213.198,84 €	0,39	0,14	SPB_Salaries_EUR18_L1	- 12.204.947,64 €	0,010
CountMonthsCubic	- 245.513,82 €	- 0,0033	0,12	CountMonths	- 24.190.389,58 €	0,73
(Constant)	- 364.761.899.953,78 €	- 4.902,97	0,03	CountMonthsSquarred	cancelled out	
				CountMonthsCubic	9.164,85 €	0,097
				(Constant)	13.288.340.373,38 €	0,011

Significance level: 99-percent-level 95-percent-level 90-percent-level

Table 19: Result Overview

Table 19 is a combination of Table 14, Table 17 and Table 18 to highlight all regression results side-by-side in one lucid table and support the readers effort in following the chain of argumentation. A general observation might be that lags are included for very recent periods mostly and this confirms the idea that impact manifests within several periods. The longer an impact persists, the lower its impact on belated periods. Let us start chronologically once more in digesting and comparing the output-tables.

We can see in the very first row that for both cities, construction can become a valid indicator for economic growth. For Saint Petersburg, construction-turnover at period t-1 is a good predictor and for Hamburg it is t-3. This indicates that the impact of construction is faster seen in Saint Petersburg compared to Hamburg. This might be a fist indication that the Hamburg Economy is rather steady and the Saint Petersburg Economy comparably fast-pacing. When I first saw the result of 1 additional Euro in construction turnover in the measure unit “Index Point Growth”, the result seemed at a value of 0,0000015 realistic. Scaling it as described in Section 6.1.2. to Euros makes it actually surprisingly unrealistic at an impact of -109 EUR per EUR. This might indicate that either the conversion method is subject to even more flaws than already counted, or that construction indeed became a non-lucrative business in Hamburg over the years due to ever-increasing compliance regulations. Both variables are significant at the 95-percent level, but for Hamburg the impact is negative and for Saint Petersburg positive. A third possibility is that the impact of further months would even out the deficit to a realistic amount. This would then infer that the whole regression approach would require a systematically different technique and suggest extension in form of a more econometrically specialized research project. It might be interesting to explore and compare the presented

results against other investigative methods such as the Granger causality, which is often used by Macroeconomists in time-series for causal inference, although such inferences were argued to not show real causality. Exploring if results would show similar ambiguous impact directions for diverging lags might become one of the leading questions. Overall, the present result-numbers suggest that construction has a small positive effect for economic growth in Saint Petersburg, but an immensely negative impact for Hamburg.³⁷

Industrial Production was unfortunately not significant for all tested lags in the case of Hamburg. Including Lag 2 was still beneficial in decreasing the error term and forcefully include a theoretically decisive variable. For the case of Saint Petersburg, Industrial Production at $t=0$ and $t-1$ appear significant as already argued in Results Section 6.2. Both periods are significant at the 95-percent level and their impacts appears realistically devastating at describing the Saint Petersburg Industrial sector, which experiences a very negative development over the whole observation period as described in Section 4.2.6.2. It is arguably at no surprise to most people that the Russian industry does have core-competencies, but was and is rather at a competitive disadvantage to open world markets. Provocative appears an idea at which the now closed down economy after the fateful day of 24.02.2022 might actually relief the Saint Petersburg industry of global competition and thereby revive the autarky seeking industrial purpose and development.

Further investigating the Service Sector, it appears hard to assess the validity of impact of the blurred Service Index. As the index moves on a scale of small attitude the change in impact would be expected to be of very large magnitude, but whether 260 million in turnover-growth are realistic is truly hard to tell. We investigated here the impact of a compiled index on the growth rate of another compiled and then converted index. The open space for inaccuracies is enormous. As for the case of Saint Petersburg, we can say that the result becomes only realistic as soon as we start summing the timepoint-dependent results against each other. We find ever more evidence for the argument that impacts are inflated and altering between subsequent lag-inclusions. We see a large positive impact, followed by an even larger negative impact. For all variables, where more than one period is included, we always see that one impact is positive and the other negative. This might become one of the more relevant findings of this thesis. For more extensive evaluation it would be truly beneficial to use more advanced econometric methods that account for all lags within the observation-period.

Talking about unemployment, we already argued that results for both cities are fairly similar and realistic given certain assumption like a higher incentive to register as unemployed in Hamburg. In the final model, for both cases three periods increase model-efficiency. For both cases, signs alternate in a sinus-cosinus appearing pattern. We can definitely say that the Hamburg results

are more reliable because all three periods are significant at the 99-percent level. For Saint Petersburg only two out of three included periods are significant and only at the 90-percent level.

Interpreting the results concerning the salary-level, we can point out a core difference. Increasing the average monthly salary in Hamburg by 1 EUR is associated with a growth increase of 1 index point in growth at the 95-percent level. The increase concerns roughly a working population of 1 million people. If converted to monetary units, this increase might be around the magnitude of 75,3 million Euros. This would mean that salary increases of 1 EUR are associated with a 75 Euro increase in economic-growth. Frankly speaking, this appears to be unrealistically high, hinting to further unaccounted-for periods. In Saint Petersburg, in contrast, an increase in salary by 1 EUR for a working population of around 3 million people is associated with an economic growth slowdown by 12 million Euros at the 99-percent level. Here the ratio is more realistic and merely 1 to 4, as compared to 1 to 75 in Hamburg. One aspect to bear in mind is the difference in tax surcharge on each additionally earned unit, which is progressive in Germany and one of the key income sources for the state that is leveraged for new indebteding and succeeding budget allocations. Overall, we can conclude that, if trusting the data, we can argue that increasing salary levels in Hamburg might positively impact the meritocratic economy, as people seem to expect rewards for their developed skills and try to live up to expectations in exchange for compensation. In Saint Petersburg, the salary levels should not be uplifted to prevent economic slow-down. Speaking in terms of mentality, it might be the case that the amount of money earned has no direct connection to productivity of an individual. Some people earn a lot undeservingly and others work a lot for very little. There is little belief in a fair society that regulates compensation in alignment with effort. Dzmitryieva (2018) describes a general Russian selection-process as somewhere between meritocracy and nepotism. Heuer et al. (2020) in contrast describe a rather strong relationship in Germany between development of skills, societal status and reward. A finding that probably most people would attribute to Germany intuitively anyways. Furthermore, we should actually not cluster all jobs the same. Some form of heterogeneity has to exist and the effects of increasing salary-levels in e.g., blue collar jobs and white-collar jobs might differ. ^{38 39}

Talking about the included time-dummies, we can summarize that they seem to have very little association with economic growth rate in Hamburg's stable economy. In Saint Petersburg, especially a cubic time-trend growth seems to persist at the 90-percent level. The economy in Saint Petersburg seems to be more seasonal and rougher. Economic shocks seem to lead to stronger and faster reactions, which was already visible when examining the variables in Chapter 4.2.

A final, already described difference is certainly the constant, which provides us with the level of economic growth given a scenario where all included variables were set to zero. In both cases, the constant is significant at the 95-percent level for Hamburg and almost at the 99-percent level for Saint Petersburg. We could think about the constant as an innate, natural ability of the dependent variable to grow. This growth-pressure is negative for Hamburg with a collapse time of only several periods, while the results suggest a remaining positive growth for the turnover-growth-rate of companies in the Saint Petersburg economy. A substantial difference, which might be rooted in the different nature of both dependent variables. One is a financial index and the other a fundamental economic measurement. It wouldn't be too surprising if experienced fundamental pressures would vary.

To make a few closing remarks, I would like to point out that including other specific lags into the regression might lead to opposite signs in association-results. A substantial problem and a finding in its own way. Furthermore, we have to remain cautious of possibilities that some statistics might in fact be made-up, although I have found little evidence, yet. Moreover, some of the assumptions made throughout this thesis might appear arbitrary. For example, taking a conversion rate from a different period might substantially change inferences. Finally, there is always a possibility that calculations might include mistakes and in the best case an experienced econometrician should retrace most compilations, calculations and assumptions. A task that might be only reasonably rewarding for a co-author with mentioned skills. At last, it remains true that observing the included variables in exactly the chosen model-constellations have predictive power and are relatively efficient given the chosen methods.

7.1. Research Extensions

There are of course extensions thinkable that would enhance the exploration. The very first extension might be to add sales of resources like oil and gas into the analysis. It might be the case that the Russian economy as a whole, and especially the two main cities Saint Petersburg and Moscow are recipients of subsidies that result from sales of natural resources. Including such variables into this thesis would, however, lead to even more asymmetries, because sales of natural resources are obviously more relevant for economic growth in Saint Petersburg than in Hamburg. Further unobserved economic variables might undoubtedly be also of interest.

It is hard to say what long-run absolute effects of variable-tweaks are, because the chosen method always explores specific points in time and usually only includes the most recent couple of lags. An approach, which could capture the cumulative impact over the whole observation period might become a good extension to this research. More advanced econometric instruments used by more experienced econometricians might lead to more fruitful results.

Having to get rid of non-stationarity by differencing and subsequently being compelled to merely perceive changes certainly complicates the investigation, compared to talking about absolute values.

Another interesting point would be to actually focus on profits instead of turnover. Although turnover might be high, it does not automatically mean that a company is even profiting. Nevertheless, such an undertaking stands and falls with data-availability, which does not seem openly available at this time. It would be great if more data on economic developments would be made publicly available to everyone. In the best case in monthly frequency to give scientists and students the resources to truly research the markets. One might think that the revelation principle was a deep microeconomic idea on mechanisms encouraging to play with open cards. Making data available to everyone does hint the risk of reverse-engineering critical industry-mechanisms, but might also help in our understanding of the markets. Countless eyes see more than two do. It is, as many things in life a trade-off between trust and privilege. The modern economy moves fast and thus most analysis should nowadays be conducted with monthly data and on monthly frequency instead of yearly. Tracking authorities should adjust their efforts to such requirements. Economic data and data in general cannot continue to be a closed-off good. Data should be open-source and available to anyone willing to investigate.

Further research might also include taking cultural differences more into account. A great framework is “Hofstede's cultural dimensions”, which in combination with measured hard-data might aid in explaining reasons for covering-up economic downshifts, tax-evasion legitimacy and economic growth as a mean to itself in search for societal well-being. ⁴⁰

In summary, we can conclude that more intriguing results can be expected from including more relevant variables, better data-transparency and availability, more advanced scientific methods, prolonged time dedication, cross-inclusion of other scientific disciplines like political science, mathematics or sociology, and repeating such investigations for further cities all around the globe.

7.2. Robustness of Results

I have to admit once more that this research has too many variable assumptions like specific chosen conversion rates, or that inflation is homogenously represented by the CPI, or that turnover of companies is an adequate representation of economic growth. Additionally, we have this heuristic approach, where we try to convert index points of an abstract flawed financial index to something related to economic turnover of companies. This is certainly one of the most vulnerable assumptions. A comparison of both regressions in numeric terms requires similar assumptions to those presented, or better substitutes. Just the conversion rate of RUB to EUR

can vary somewhere between 34 – 144 to 1. Simply taking a different conversion rate would shift the balance of the comparison in terms of values manifold. Such differences should, however, not scratch very general conclusions like that the impacts can be ambiguous in direction. Further assumptions might also include underlying ideas that data throughout observation periods are tracked mostly consistently and that there were no major changes in definitions.

One robustness check that would present itself might be to look at the intuitive models of both regressions, before they were tweaked. Although they are certainly less efficient and have larger residuals, they might support or question the presented findings.

Regression Coefficients					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error			
SPB Construction Jan18 EUR	-,324	,832	-,054	-,390	,698
SPB Industrial Production Jan18 EUR	1,472	,397	2,283	3,709	,000
SPB Salaries Jan18 EUR	-4534464,741	4257798,501	-,197	-1,065	,291
Services SPB Jan18 EUR	8,272	5,782	,227	1,431	,158
SPB Unemployment	22279,608	13760,655	,311	1,619	,111
CountMonths	1968534473,8	527951078,31	19,318	3,729	,000
CountMonthsSquarred	-33914015,413	9243162,699	-,33,175	-3,669	,001
CountMonthsCubic	196362,087	53937,544	16,179	3,641	,001
(Constant)	-45968145067	11684092630		-3,934	,000

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

Table 20: Result-table of Intuitive SPB Model.

Table 20 and Table 21 consist of the intuitive Regression models for Saint Petersburg and Hamburg respectively. The first observation is that most of the variables are not significant anymore. The only remaining significant covariates are in the case of Saint Petersburg Industrial Production, the dummies and the constant. Industrial Production seems to have a similar positive association, as in the optimal regression form. Looking at the time trend, we find N and N^3 positive and N^2 negative. Hence validity of time dummy conclusions seems ambiguous. All other variables are insignificant and thus little telling. The constant turned from my, by great narrative supported, positive value to a strongly negative one, giving my hypothesis that maybe fundamental dependent variables are more robust compared to financial indices, which are subject to financial pressure, a questionable aftertaste.

For the case of Hamburg in Table 21, we can say that the constant remained negative and of the same magnitude. The only other significant variable in the intuitive version is Services. Services remained at a very similar associative level of 3,8 index points change (3,5 in the optimized model) per index point change in the HASPAX Index. In summary, I would say that comparing the intuitive results with the optimized is little telling, if not counterproductive for Saint Petersburg, but supportive for Hamburg. What we can still take from this is that we can make most variables become significant by including the most relevant lags (except for the case of Industrial Production for Hamburg).

Regression Coefficients					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error			
HH Construction Jan18	-2,002E-7	,000	-,041	-,279	,781
HH Industrial Production Jan18	-4,100E-8	,000	-,212	-,954	,343
Service Index HH	3,814	1,336	,529	2,854	,006
HH Unemployment	,006	,006	,266	1,011	,316
HH Salaries Jan18	1,174	,553	,613	2,121	,037
CountMonths	-14,762	9,763	-2,082	-1,512	,135
CountMonthsSquarred	,343	,273	4,291	1,259	,212
CountMonthsCubic	-,002	,002	-2,437	-1,120	,266
(Constant)	-5402,058	2666,364		-2,026	,046

The Prais-Winsten estimation method is used.

Table 21: Results-table of Intuitive HH Model.

It is expected that working with different data-sets should obviously lead to diverging specific results. The general form of the results, meaning that specific lag-inclusion in the regression model should make those variables significant by tweaking for a low RMSE should be a systemically valid and replicable trial & error approach. Furthermore, as already pointed out, a more sophisticated approach, which feasibly accounts for all possible lags at the same time and outputs a cumulative total impact associated to the change of specific fundamental variables should in theory provide more sophisticated and certainly more absolute insights. Simply focusing on the most relevant-appearing big waves does not describe the whole ocean. As for the case of forecasting anomalies, pure predictive first-mover changes in independent variables in the form of forerunners, the numeric results should, nonetheless, suffice.

Overall, with more advanced econometric techniques, experience, time commitment and data-availability, surely more sophisticated results can be expected.

8. Conclusion

In this final section, we want to reflect upon and summarize the developmental process traversing this thesis. We started off in the first chapter by exploring the long-lasting and struggling relationship between the two second-capitals of Germany and Russia – Hamburg and Saint Petersburg. We explored their mutual influence in an International Relations context and related the current unfortunate developments in an intriguing aspiration to relate both cities in an economic environment and thereby add to our understanding. We substantiated our research question into exploring impact-mechanisms of the macroeconomic variables: Construction, Industrial Production, Services, Unemployment, Average Salary and time-trends on the growth of both cities. While we ended up measuring the growth of Hamburg by instrument of the HASPAX index, we were free to investigate the impacts of named variables on the turnover of companies in Saint Petersburg.

Thereafter, in Chapter 2, we explored the literature and came to the assessment that despite the general idea, very little research can be found on such a specific comparison. We found that most research concerning the relation between both cities is indeed concerned with merely the relationship between both cities in an International Relations context with very superficial exceptions. We concluded that modern research has to deal with modern years, high frequencies and a narrower city-level economy to fight country-wide heterogeneities. The approach in this thesis might be a first fundamental stone in a general approach for economic city-comparisons.

In Chapter 3, we clarified the technical approach in form of multivariable regressions with the Software IBM SPSS Statistics, named key issues (such as serial correlation) and possible approaches for solutions.

Chapter 4 was then dedicated to the extensive data-collection and conversion process naming the data-origins and a general a priori exploration all variables in visual form with interpretation attempts. First diagnosis, such as suspicious repetitive patterns in the Russian data and first evidence that the Hamburg economy appears more robust and shock-resistant were swiftly formed. Furthermore, we discussed data-reliance issues and that we cannot exclude possibilities of contrived data. Additionally, we formulated necessary assumptions to hold for further analysis. We ended the section with a brief demographic comparison as an overview for similar challenges, which have to be faced by the populations of both cities.

In Chapter 5 thereafter, we switched to the technical part, in which we clarified how our regressions might look like and built models for both cities from scratch in an iterative process. We explored questions of non-stationarity and got rid of serial correlation by solving for stationarity through differencing our dependent variables. One result originating in this section is the evidence that always the same variables were stationary or non-stationary in both city-economies. Subsequently, we explored in a curve estimation the time-trend of both economies and concluded that a cubic time-trend is the best-fitting for expressing the data-development along time. In the final part, which demanded the conduction of hundreds of regressions, we optimized both regression models for the most optimal lag-inclusions in a trial-and-error process by optimizing for the Root Square Mean Error (RMSE). This went along with forcing insignificant variables to become significant by choosing the most telling lags in a replicable approach. In a final, but lengthy part, we ascertained, whether our developed models would fulfil all necessary Asymptotic Gauss-Markov Assumptions for Time-Series to ensure validity of possible results. Both models were thereby proven to not violate any critical conjectures.

With all requirements for interpretation of results fulfilled, we started exploring results suggested by the optimized regressions in Chapter 6. For both models, it was possible to get most variables to become significant and therefore act as predictors to future developments in specific constellations. Especially cases, where subsequent lags of the same variable became associated with opposite growth patterns are major findings of this thesis, which will be further emphasized in the final part of the concluding chapter. This finding implies that regression coefficients are so ambiguous and fast-changing that finding such values of impact in a specific period becomes irrelevant. It does not really matter, whether an increase in industrial turnover leads to growth in the subsequent period, if there is a second, additional impact in the second period, as well. Furthermore, a similar impact (which can be positive or negative) already

appeared in a foregoing period. Such findings suggest that only aggregated impacts of all relevant periods matter to show an absolute impact of an increase in a specific macroeconomic variable. Moreover, inclusion of additional periods of the same variables obviously leads to increased collinearity and thus blurs results. This was evident in the optimized Saint Petersburg model, which ended up with more relevant lags and thus higher collinearity. Hence, a more sophisticated mathematical approach appears appropriate. We measured growth in Saint Petersburg in monetary units, but growth in Hamburg in financial index points due to a lack of data-availability and out of necessity. We converted those index points under strong assumptions heuristically into monetary units, but the results appeared partly inflated thereafter.

Chapter 7 dealt with an extensive discussion of results showing surprisingly that associations of literally all variables at question are alternating in direction without exception between both models. If increasing salary levels leads to a positive boost in Hamburg, the same impact is associated to lead to a negative downturn in Saint Petersburg. Construction boosts the Saint Petersburg economy, but is a bad investment in Hamburg. Services are a good stimulator for the Hamburg economy, but are inefficient in Saint Petersburg according to the results. Such results are implying fundamentally different underlying economic mechanisms on first sight. However, relativizing such a finding with the implication of ambiguous impact directions by including various lags leads to the belief that impact of macroeconomic is more complex than a simple fixed multiplier. The differences in impact-magnitude are most likely linked to the conversion of index points to monetary units in the less reliable Hamburg model.

In Neoclassical, New Keynesian macroeconomic models such as the “dynamic stochastic general equilibrium” (DSGE), the dynamic of shocks is usually taught as convex, or concave curves, which do however not appear as overly complex. Figure 46 is a good example of how several such impact curves might look like. They have either clear positive, or negative effects. They, however, do not show such ambiguous impacts, as were implied by the results in this research. In contrast, real world numbers suggest that the impact of for example unemployment can have strong positive effects in the first month and then even stronger negative impacts in the second month, followed by modest positive impacts once more in a third period. Curves like in Figure 46 have this underlying assumption that a shock wears off with time and loses intensity as time goes on. Results of my analysis suggest, however, that shocks might have their most impactful moments very unexpectedly. Just as real economic data is rough, so is the interaction between economic variables. It is even thoughtfully expected that for example a shock in construction would unleash its impact on growth not in the initial period. Furthermore, although the overall effect might be positive, it might have at first a negative initial effect. The real interaction along

time might rather look something like Figure 47, where positive and negative effects balance each other out in each new period independently. Just as real world-economic data is rough, so

Figure 46: Dynamic effects of contractionary monetary policy shock. Prof. Bauer (Uni Hamburg): Adv. Macro Elements of Dynamic Macroeconomic Theory. WS2020, Lecture 16, Slide 27.

Figure 47: Sketched effect of variable on growth in reality.

it is more likely that interaction between those variables might be rough as well. I believe such simplified impact curves as illustrated in Figure 46 to be too ideal and oversimplified for an accurate reflection of reality.

In general, it cannot intuitively be concluded by the regression results, whether specific data-values are made-up, or not. It is in theory possible to tweak made-up numbers to become significant and therefore finding a significant association of two values does not automatically proof validity. Therefore, it is not trivial to deduce a specific meritocratic level merely by observing fundamental macroeconomic values. Certain patterns in the Russian data remain due to their repetitive patterns suspicious of creative accounting or similar tweaks. In spite of that, we should also bear in mind that certain industries are indeed seasonal (like construction) and effects might be stronger in Russia, where temperature volatility is higher. Furthermore, legislative reasons like fixed dates for reporting might also be a factor.

A general proposal of this research is to fight barriers of data-availability by standardized, universal, transparent and available tracking of fundamental macroeconomic variables, such as is the case in most financial industries around the world.

Statement of independent work

I hereby declare that this thesis contains my own independent work. I was, however, warmly guided in my exploration by doctorate Christina Maaß, a fellow researcher at the Chair of Professor Straubhaar from the University of Hamburg. Furthermore, I received help from Professor Alexandra Koval and Professor Vladimir Sherov-Ignatev from Saint Petersburg State University, who hinted me to places, where I finally found relevant economic reports for Saint Petersburg. Furthermore, I was recipient of several econometric ideas by Professor Bernd Lucke from the University of Hamburg, thanks to whom I was able to extend the timeline of my data-set twofold. I have not used any material or sources apart from those which have been indicated on the list of references. All data-sources are enclosed in digital form on the data storage medium. Furthermore, I confirm that I have not submitted this thesis to any previous examination procedure and that the submitted printed version is identical to the electronic version.

Mark Spektor

15.11.2022

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9. Appendix

9.1. Reference to RAW-Data on USB-Media

Almost all relevant figures made it into the thesis. They are for the most part illustrations of data that can be examined in the Excel Master-Sheet. There is a substantial set of data-files, reports and Excel-tables complementing this thesis, which are all enclosed to this thesis.

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9.2. Definitions of utilized variables

Hamburg | HASPAX Index

“The HASPAX is a share index that tracks the performance of listed companies from the Hamburg metropolitan region. In addition to the share price development, it also takes dividend distributions into account and is designed as a performance index. To prevent a small number of companies from dominating the index, the maximum weighting per share is limited to 15 percent of the index capitalization.”

Source: <https://www.n-tv.de/boersenkurse/indizes/haspax-13278129>

Saint Petersburg | Turnover of Organizations

Turnover of Organizations within the Region of Saint Petersburg always in monthly socio-economic report of that month page 6 (=36 source reports in years 2018 - 2021)

Source: <https://petrostat.gks.ru/folder/32168/>

Hamburg | Salaries

Gross monthly earnings of full-time employees in the manufacturing and service sectors

“Quarterly averages are shown, i.e., March = average from Jan. to March, June = average from April to June, etc., excluding special payments. The annual average includes special payments. Due to structural changes within the reporting population, the comparability of data with earlier reporting periods is impaired as of the 1st quarter of 2012. Including civil servants”

Source: <https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/erwerbstaetigkeit-verdienste-arbeitskosten/monatszahlen-erwerbstaetigkeit-und-verdienste?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A47&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A47&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A53&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A53&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A204&prevInputTree%5B%5D=t%3A205&filter%5Blocation%5D=2&showAllYears=&showAllYears=1&filter%5BadditionalTopics%5D=>

Saint Petersburg | Salaries

“Average monthly nominal accrued salary of employees of organizations in Saint Petersburg”

Source: Excel: info-stat-03-2022 / 12 зарплата / 12-01 среднемесячная заработная плата.xls / Sheet: рублей

Consumer Price Index (CPI) = Inflation | Hamburg

“Consumer price statistics are used to determine the average price development of all goods and services purchased by private households for consumption purposes on a monthly basis. The results are presented as indices and rates of change. They are important indicators for assessing economic developments and provide guidance for economic and social policy measures. The basis for the index calculations is a statistical basket of goods, in which over 700 goods are compiled as price representatives and are updated on an ongoing basis. These represent both the total consumption of private households and the price development of all goods with sufficient accuracy. All goods are included in the overall index according to their expenditure share (weight) in total consumption in the base year (weighting scheme). In contrast to the basket of goods, the weighting scheme is only updated every five years in order to be able to show the pure price development within this period without being influenced by a change in the expenditure weights.”

In Germany, a base year (2015) is taken and all time-periods reflect a comparison to the base year (=100)

Source: <https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/volkswirtschaft-preise/dokumentenansicht/verbraucherpreisindex-fuer-hamburg-61364>

Consumer Price Index (CPI) = Inflation | Saint Petersburg

“The index of consumer prices and tariffs on goods and paid services to the population (CPI) characterizes the change over time in the general level of prices and tariffs on goods and services purchased by the population for non-productive consumption. It measures the ratio of the cost of a fixed set of goods and services in the current period to its cost in the previous period. Set of goods and services includes more than 500 goods (services)-representatives. Prices and tariffs are monitored in republic capitals, centers of territories, regions, autonomous districts, federal cities and selectively in district centers, selected with account of their representativeness in reflection of socio-economic and geographic position of regions.”

Sources:

2015: Socio Economic Development Report 2017 Jan - Dec SV: page 4

2016 + 2017: Socio Economic Development Report 2018 Jan - Dec SV: page 4

2018: Socio Economic Development Report 2018 Jan - Dec: page 36

2019: Socio Economic Development Report 2019 Jan - Dec: page 36

2020: Socio Economic Development Report 2020 Jan - Dec: page 36

2021: Socio Economic Development Report 2021 Jan - Dec: page 36

Unemployed | Hamburg

Statistikamt Nord > Zahlen + Fakten > Erwerbstätigkeit, Verdienste, Arbeitskosten > Monatszahlen

„Unit: number; Explanation: Results are preliminary; the latest values can be found on the Federal Employment Agency's website (www.statistik.arbeitsagentur.de) as detailed overviews.

Source: Labor market statistics of the Federal Employment Agency“

Source: <https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/erwerbstaetigkeit-verdienste-arbeitskosten/monatszahlen-erwerbstaetigkeit-und-verdienste?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A5&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A5&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A8&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A8&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A31&prevInputTree%5B%5D=%3F%3A-1&filter%5Blocation%5D=2>

Unemployed | Saint Petersburg

“Dynamics of the number of unemployed citizens registered in state institutions of the employment service” + “of them having status "unemployed" by institutions at end of month”

Source:

2015: Socio Economic Development Report 2016 Jan - Dec SV page 15

2016: Socio Economic Development Report 2016 Jan - Dec SV page 14

2017: Socio Economic Development Report 2018 Jan - Dec: page 51

2018: Socio Economic Development Report 2019 Jan - Dec: page 52

2019: Socio Economic Development Report 2020 Jan - Dec: page 51

2020: Socio Economic Development Report 2021 Jan - Dec: page 50

2021: Socio Economic Development Report 2021 Jan - Dec: page 50

<https://petrostat.gks.ru/folder/32168/>

Industrial Production | Hamburg

= (1) + (2)

(1) = Manufacturing industry - sales (excluding sales tax) in Hamburg.xlsx

“Establishments with 50 or more employees. As of January 2009, the data are delimited according to a revised classification of economic activities (WZ 2008). To enable a correct comparison with the previous year, the results for 2008 have been recoded to this new classification.”

Source: [https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/industrie-baugewerbe-handwerk/monatszahlen-industrie-bau-und-](https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/industrie-baugewerbe-handwerk/monatszahlen-industrie-bau-und-handwerk?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A20&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A20&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A95&prevInputTree%5B%5D=t%3A93&filter%5Blocation%5D=2&showAllYears=&filter%5BadditionalTopics%5D=)

[handwerk?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A20&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A20&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A95&prevInputTree%5B%5D=t%3A93&filter%5Blocation%5D=2&showAllYears=&filter%5BadditionalTopics%5D=](https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/industrie-baugewerbe-handwerk?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A20&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A20&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A95&prevInputTree%5B%5D=t%3A93&filter%5Blocation%5D=2&showAllYears=&filter%5BadditionalTopics%5D=)

(2) = Energy and water supply - gross total remuneration.xlsx

“Energy and water supply - gross total remuneration; Establishments of companies with generally 20 or more employees; results in current reporting year preliminary”

Source: [https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/industrie-baugewerbe-](https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/industrie-baugewerbe-handwerk/monatszahlen-industrie-bau-und-handwerk?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A21&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A21&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A107&prevInputTree%5B%5D=%3F%3A-1&filter%5Blocation%5D=2)

[handwerk/monatszahlen-industrie-bau-und-handwerk?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A21&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A21&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A107&prevInputTree%5B%5D=%3F%3A-1&filter%5Blocation%5D=2](https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/industrie-baugewerbe-handwerk?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A21&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A21&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A107&prevInputTree%5B%5D=%3F%3A-1&filter%5Blocation%5D=2)

Construction | Hamburg

Main construction industry - Construction sales (excluding sales tax).xlsx

“Construction of buildings, civil engineering, demolition and preparatory site work, etc.; companies with 20 or more employees”

Source: [https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/industrie-baugewerbe-](https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/industrie-baugewerbe-handwerk/monatszahlen-industrie-bau-und-handwerk?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A22&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A22&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A116&prevInputTree%5B%5D=%3F%3A-1&filter%5Blocation%5D=2)

[handwerk/monatszahlen-industrie-bau-und-handwerk?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A22&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A22&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A116&prevInputTree%5B%5D=%3F%3A-1&filter%5Blocation%5D=2](https://www.statistik-nord.de/zahlen-fakten/industrie-baugewerbe-handwerk?inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A19&inputTree%5B%5D=c%3A22&prevInputTree%5B%5D=c%3A22&inputTree%5B%5D=t%3A116&prevInputTree%5B%5D=%3F%3A-1&filter%5Blocation%5D=2)

Construction | Saint Petersburg

Organization of various types of activities (excluding small businesses) completed construction and installation works

"Volume of works performed using own in-house capabilities by type of activity construction - the value of works performed by companies using their own resources for the type of activity "Construction" on the basis of agreements (or contracts) signed with the value of works performed by companies using their own resources for the "Construction" type of activity on the basis of agreements and (or) contracts made with customers. The cost of such works includes construction and assembly works, as well as other contract work performed under general, direct and subcontractor agreements at the expense of all sources of financing. The cost of these works includes general, direct, and subcontractor contracts from all sources of the overhaul, repair, reconstruction, modernization of residential and nonresidential buildings and engineering structures are financed from all sources of funding."

Source:

2016: Excel: 3. info-stat-12-2020\03 03-01: объем работ, выполненных по ВЭД Строительство.xlsx: Млн. рублей

2017: Socio Economic Development Report 2018 Jan - Dec: page 13

2018: Socio Economic Development Report 2019 Jan - Dec: page 13

2019: Socio Economic Development Report 2020 Jan - Dec: page 15

2020: Socio Economic Development Report 2021 Jan - Dec: page 14

2021: Socio Economic Development Report 2021 Jan - Dec: page 14

Services | Hamburg

Climate in the service industry

"The calculated business climate indicator for Hamburg's economy and the respective sectors is derived from the assessments of the current situation and future development. The resulting values range from 0 to 200 index points."

Source:

Hamburg Chamber of Commerce

<https://www.ihk.de/hamburg/produktmarken/branchen-cluster-netzwerke/branchen/dienstleistungswirtschaft/branchenueberblick-1394654>

Services | Saint Petersburg

Paid services to the public

"The volume of paid services to the population reflects the volume of consumption by the population of different types of services rendered by residents of the Russian economy. The volume of paid services to the population includes the export of services and does not include their import. Statistically, this indicator is measured by the amount of money paid by the consumer for the service rendered. Payment can be made by the consumer or by the organization, in which the consumer works, which fully or partially compensates or pays for the consumption of services. This indicator is formed on the basis of data from federal state statistical observation forms and expert evaluation of hidden and informal activities on the service market according to the approved methodology."

Source:

2016: Excel Data Reports\1. info-stat-03-2022\06 услуги\06-01 объем платных услуг.xls
Sheet: к соотв. Месяцу; Saint Petersburg is in row 37 + **reconstruction into units**

2017: Socio Economic Development Report 2019 Jan - Dec: page 28

2018: Socio Economic Development Report 2020 Jan - Dec: page 29

2019: Socio Economic Development Report 2021 Jan - Dec: page 29

2020: Socio Economic Development Report 2022 Jan - Dec: page 29

2021: Socio Economic Development Report 2022 Jan - Dec: page 29

Note: SV refers to short versions of reports.